

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 3: Evolutionary Computation module – part 2: Multi-objective optimization

Michał K. Tomczyk

Institute of Computing Science, Poznan University of Technology, Poznań, Poland

This document is part of a tutorial series on JECDM. URL: www.jecdm.cs.put.poznan.pl, email: jecdm@cs.put.poznan.pl.
The framework version used when preparing the document: 1.0 (initial release; Java v. 17.0; IntelliJ IDEA 2023.2).

Abstract

This tutorial discusses the Evolutionary Computation module’s capabilities from the evolutionary multi-objective optimization perspective.

Keywords: JECDM, evolutionary computation, evolutionary multi-objective algorithm, multi-objective optimization

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Understanding fundamental concepts	1
2.1	Standardization in evaluation	1
2.2	Standardization in normalization	2
2.2.1	Normalization interface	2
2.2.2	Objective space	4
2.2.3	Normalization builder interface	4
2.2.4	Example uses #1 [T]	5
2.2.5	Objective space manager	7
2.2.6	Example uses #2 [T]	10
2.2.7	Update objective phase	13
2.3	Multi-objective optimization problem bundle	14
2.4	Decomposition-related components	18
2.4.1	Optimization goal	18
2.4.2	Assignment	19
2.4.3	Goals family	20
2.4.4	Goals manager	20
2.5	Performance indicators	22
2.5.1	Hypervolume	22
2.5.2	Example uses #3	23
2.5.3	Generational distance and Inverted Generational Distance	25
2.5.4	Example uses #4	25
3	Implemented methods	33
3.1	NSGA	33
3.1.1	Example use [T]	37
3.2	NSGA-II	45

3.2.1	Example use [T]	45
3.3	NSGA-III	48
3.3.1	Example use [T]	50
3.4	MOEA/D	57
3.4.1	Example use [T]	61
3.5	Comparative analysis [T]	68

1. Introduction

This document is the second part of the tutorial on the Evolutionary Computation module and is devoted to evolutionary multi-objective optimization. It is assumed that the reader is already acquainted with the first part. Thus, the concepts introduced in the previous tutorial document will not be explained here for the second time to avoid repetitions. Naturally, this document will also not provide the background for the multi-objective optimization as it is assumed that the framework’s user already has experience in this field. Consequently, the focus is purely on understanding and using the framework.

2. Understanding fundamental concepts

This section discusses various concepts that are vital for appropriately using this framework.

2.1. Standardization in evaluation

Before proceeding, it is imperative to highlight that the components designed for the multi-objective evolutionary computation assume that the specimen’s evaluation vector (the wrapped alternative’s performance vector), i.e., *Specimen.getEvaluations()*, is equivalent to the objective vector. Consequently, one should reserve this vector for this purpose

Email address: michal.tomczyk@cs.put.poznan.pl (Michał K. Tomczyk)
URL: www.cs.put.poznan.pl/mtomczyk (Michał K. Tomczyk)

when making one’s implementations to avoid errors. For instance, if the optimization problem tackled has three objectives, the specimens’ evaluations should be three-element vectors, where i -th elements are linked with i -th objective functions ($i = 0, 1, 2$).

2.2. Standardization in normalization

Normalization plays an essential role in multi-objective optimization when it comes to controlling the distribution of constructed solutions. The feasible objective space of a problem may be spanned entirely differently, given the perspective of each objective function. For instance, when considering a knapsack problem as a two-objective optimization problem, all possible knapsack total sizes (realizations) may be spanned on a range of a completely different magnitude than when considering total values. If no rescaling is implemented, such scale incompatibility may bias the final distribution of solutions towards some specific objective functions (instead of leading to uniformly distributed solutions).

Different implementations of evolutionary methods for multi-objective optimization execute the rescaling in various ways (and at different algorithmic levels). For instance, some ready-to-use implementations dynamically update so-called utopia and nadir points, allowing for determining bounds that encapsulate all non-dominated vectors in the objective space constructed throughout evolution. Other methods require fixing some scaling factors used, e.g., in scalarized functions employed in decomposition-based algorithms. This framework, however, imposes a strict standardization for the rescaling process employed by all methods that are implemented and will be in the future as a part of JECDM.

Standardization can be understood here from two perspectives: how the rescaling is conducted (the assumptions made) and which components are responsible for managing this process. Regarding the first, it is assumed that if the rescaling is used (but it may not also be), all the rescaling-dependent processes (e.g., calculating crowding-distance in NSGA-II [1]) will operate assuming that the objective vectors are contained in a $[0, 1]^M$ hypercube, where M denotes the number of objectives, $\mathbf{0}$ -vector is a utopia point (the best objective vector), and $\mathbf{1}$ -vector is nadir (the worst objective vector considered).

Regarding the rescaling handler, the intention was to delegate understanding of how to normalize/rescale the objective vectors to components developed as method-independent. For this purpose, the default “update objective space” phase, mentioned in the previous tutorial document, was designed. By default, it is supposed to be executed each time new solutions are created and evaluated, allowing knowledge of the objective space bounds to be updated. Furthermore, the default implementation can be parameterized in various ways, allowing control over the rescaling process to be taken. Lastly, it allows providing listeners that will be notified each time the information on the objective space bounds is changed, which can help propagate these updates across all interested components when designing a new method.

The process briefly discussed above is depicted in Figure 1. Note that the presented processing flow is simplified to give just

a general insight into it now.

Figure 1: Updating knowledge on the objective space bounds – simplified scheme

The following sections introduce step by step all relevant classes/components, etc., that are essential for understanding how the rescaling is apprehended in JECDM.

2.2.1. Normalization interface

It is assumed that projecting data points in the original space into $[0, 1]^M$ hypercube will be handled by normalization objects. For this reason, a straightforward interface *INormalization* was introduced (see Listing 1; *space.normalization* package in the *Utils* interface). It provides just one description of a method that is supposed to perform a simple mapping: double (supposed to be in the original space) \rightarrow double (normalized value).

Listing 1: INormalization interface

```

/**
 * Interface for classes responsible for
 * normalizing doubles.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public interface INormalization
{
    /**
     * Normalizes input value.
     *
     * @param value input value
     * @return normalized value
     */
    double getNormalized(double value);
}
  
```

To help constructing custom $value \rightarrow [0, 1]$ mappings (as intended in this module), an auxiliary abstract class named *AbstractMinMaxNormalization* was implemented (see the *space.normalization.minmax* package in the *Utils* module). Its code is provided in Listing 2. All its inheritors are supposed to perform the above mapping using the specified min and max reference values. The standard implementation of such a normalization procedure is the well-known linear interpolation: $(input - min) / (max - min)$. The default implementation

of the “*getNormalized*” method provided in the abstract class executes exactly this mapping. A class that can be instantiated and inherits this functionality is called *Linear* (see the code in Listing 3; *space.normalization.minmax* package in the *Utils* 50 module).

Listing 2: AbstracMinMaxNormalization class

```

public abstract class
    AbstractMinMaxNormalization implements
        INormalization
{
    /**
     * Min value.
     */
    protected double _min;

    /**
     * Max value.
     */
    protected double _max;

    /**
     * Difference between max and min.
     */
    protected double _dv;

    /**
     * Default constructor (sets min to 0.0,
     * and max to 1.0).
     */
    public AbstractMinMaxNormalization()
    {
        this(0.0d, 1.0d);
    }

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param min min value
     * @param max max value
     */
    public AbstractMinMaxNormalization(double
        min, double max)
    {
        setMinMax(min, max);
    }

    /**
     * Normalizes input value (linear
     * normalization). In the case when min
     * == max, the value is always mapped to
     * 0.0f.
     *
     * @param value input value
     * @return normalized value
     */
    @Override
    public double getNormalized(double value)
    {
        if (Double.compare(_dv, 0.0d) == 0)
            return 0.0f;

```

```

        return (value - _min) / _dv;
    }

    /**
     * Unnormalized input value. I.e., input
     * in the range [0, 1] is mapped into a
     * value in the initially considered
     * space.
     *
     * In the case when min == max, the
     * result is always mapped into min.
     *
     * @param value normalized value [0, 1]
     * @return value in the initially
     *         considered space
     */
    public double getUnnormalized(double
        value)
    {
        if (Double.compare(_dv, 0.0d) == 0)
            return _min;
        return value * _dv + _min;
    }

    [...]
}

```

Listing 3: Linear (normalization) class

```

public class Linear extends
    AbstractMinMaxNormalization implements
        INormalization
{
    /**
     * Default constructor (sets min to 0.0
     * and max to 1.0).
     */
    public Linear()
    {
        this(0.0d, 1.0d);
    }

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param min min value
     * @param max max value
     */
    public Linear(double min, double max)
    {
        super(min, max);
    }

    /**
     * Prints info on the normalization
     * procedure.
     *
     */
    @Override
    public String toString()
    {
        return String.format("Linear
            normalization: min = %.6f; max = %.6

```

```

        f", _min, _max);
    }

    [...]
}

```

```

    */
    public final double[] _nadir;

    /**
     * Objective space ranges (spanned over
     * the utopia and nadir points).
     */
    public final Range[] _ranges;

    /**
     * Criteria types: true = gain; false =
     * cost. It impacts the position of the
     * utopia/nadir point.
     */
    public final boolean[] _criteriaTypes;

    [...]
}

```

2.2.2. Objective space

The *ObjectiveSpace* class (*space.os* package in the *Utils* module) handles the necessary data representing the current state of knowledge on the objective space bounds (original space, i.e., before normalization). Its most relevant code snippet is brought in Listing 5. There are four essential fields:

- “*utopia*”: this contains the best (feasible) values for each objective (fixed or dynamically identified; parameterization-dependent).
- “*nadir*”: as the utopia vector, but it contains the worst evaluations.
- “*ranges*”: Each range object contains data on the known min and max values for the associated objective (these min and max values are consistent with the values stored in the utopia and nadir vectors).
- “*criteriaTypes*”: This vector stores the information on the optimization/preference directions (i.e., whether the objective is to be minimized or maximized). The “true” values are associated with maximization (“false” otherwise). Note that these flags are checked when determining the utopia/nadir vectors, i.e., “true” flags state that the maximal values stored in the “*ranges*” object should be used when determining the best value (flag of “false” implies using the minimal values).

Note that this class provides various constructors that support automatically establishing some of these fields, e.g. calculating utopia/nadir vectors based on ranges and criteria types. Additionally, these vectors’ *i*-th objects are assumed to be associated with the *i*-th objective function (implicit 1:1 mapping).

Listing 4: ObjectiveSpace class

```

/**
 * Class maintaining data on the objective
 * space. When used in the EMO context,
 * the objective space ranges are often
 * spanned based on the non-dominated
 * solutions.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class ObjectiveSpace
{
    /**
     * Utopia point.
     */
    public final double[] _utopia;

    /**
     * Nadir point.
     */
}

```

2.2.3. Normalization builder interface

The objective space object serves as an input for establishing proper normalization functions (*INormalization* objects) responsible for mapping the values in the original space (objective space) onto $[0, 1]^M$ hypercube, reversing the preference direction when needed (the normalized utopia is always considered the **0**-vector – standardization).

A straightforward *INormalizationBuilder* interface for classes responsible for creating normalization objects (one per objective) based on the input objective space object is introduced (see the code provided in Listing 5; *space.normalization.builder* package in the *Utils* module). This way, hard coding may be avoided, and this transformation can be customized.

Listing 5: INormalizationBuilder interface

```

package space.normalization.builder;

import space.normalization.INormalization;
import space.os.ObjectiveSpace;

/**
 * Interface for classes building
 * normalization objects based on the
 * input data on the objective space.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */

public interface INormalizationBuilder
{
    /**
     * Builds an array of normalization
     * objects based on the input objective
     * space.
     * @param OS objective space
     * @return array of normalization objects
     */
    INormalization[] getNormalizations(
        ObjectiveSpace OS);
}

```

```
}
```

The default implementation of the *INormalizationBuilder* interface is the *StandardLinearBuilder* class (see the code in Listing 6). It constructs linear normalization objects that interpolate the input values into $[0, 1]$ bounds. Note that it also takes into account the optimization directions. If the direction is to maximize (greater values are preferred), it constructs a *LinearWithFlip* normalizer (*1-linear normalization*) to inverse the scaling result (i.e., flip around 1.0). This way, the best value (maximum) will be mapped into 0 (as assumed), while the worst (minimum) will be mapped into 1.

Listing 6: StandardLinearBuilder class

```
public class StandardLinearBuilder
    implements INormalizationBuilder
{
    /**
     * Constructs min-max normalizations (one
     * per objective)
     *
     * @param OS objective space objective
     * space
     * @return array of normalizations
     */
    @Override
    public INormalization[] getNormalizations
        (ObjectiveSpace OS)
    {
        INormalization[] normalizations = new
            INormalization[OS._criteriaTypes.
                length];

        for (int c = 0; c < OS._criteriaTypes.
            length; c++)
        {
            double L = OS._ranges[c].getLeft();
            double R = OS._ranges[c].getRight();

            if (OS._criteriaTypes[c])
                normalizations[c] = new
                    LinearWithFlip(L, R, 1.0d);
            else normalizations[c] = new Linear(L
                , R);
        }
        return normalizations;
    }
}
```

2.2.4. Example uses #1 [T]

This section introduces two short examples that showcase how the already discussed classes can be used in practice. They exhibit how the objective space can be instantiated and how the *INormalizationBuilder* object can be applied to construct adequate normalization objects. Finally, these objects are tested given a series of input data points.

Case #1.

Source package:

t1.t10.t3.evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.
t1_normalizations.t1

The source code of this example is given in Listing 7. The case implicitly assumes that there are two objectives, both to be minimized. They are spanned on, respectively, $[0, 1]$ and $[2, 4]$ bounds (hence, the expected utopia points are $[0, 2]$ and $[1, 4]$). Consider a series of input data points (in the original space) that are to be mapped into the desired $[0, 1]^2$ cube: $[0, 2]$, $[0.25, 2.5]$, $[0.5, 3]$, $[0.75, 3.5]$, $[1, 4]$, $[2, 6]$. The expected normalization products are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} [0, 2] &\rightarrow [(0 - 0) / (1 - 0) = 0, (2 - 2) / (4 - 2) = 0] \\ [0.25, 2.5] &\rightarrow [(0.25 - 0) / (1 - 0) = 0.25, (2.5 - 2) / (4 - 2) = 0.25] \\ [0.5, 3] &\rightarrow [(0.5 - 0) / (1 - 0) = 0.5, (3 - 2) / (4 - 2) = 0.5] \\ [0.75, 3.5] &\rightarrow [(0.75 - 0) / (1 - 0) = 0.75, (3.5 - 2) / (4 - 2) = 0.75] \\ [1, 4] &\rightarrow [(1 - 0) / (1 - 0) = 1, (5 - 2) / (4 - 2) = 1] \\ [2, 6] &\rightarrow [(2 - 0) / (1 - 0) = 2, (6 - 2) / (4 - 2) = 2] \end{aligned}$$

Note that the last case tests a point outside the expected bounds. It is allowed, and the normalization will proceed following the implemented formula. The code in Listing 7 shows how to execute and test such a scenario. The expected console output is given in Figure 2 for convenience.

Listing 7: Case #1

```
// Create known ranges for the OS manager (
// each associated with a different
// dimension, 1:1 mapping).
// Dimension #1 = [0, 1]
// Dimension #2 = [2, 4]
Range[] ranges = new Range[]
{
    Range.getNormalRange(),
    new Range(2.0d, 4.0)
};

// Criteria type = preference/optimization
// directions; false = to be minimized;
// true = to be maximized.
boolean[] criteriaTypes = new boolean[]{
    false, false};

// Consequently the utopia point = [0, 2],
// while the nadir point = [1, 4].

// Create the initial objective space
// object
ObjectiveSpace os = new ObjectiveSpace(
    ranges, criteriaTypes);

System.out.println("Printing information on
the objective space:");
System.out.println(os);

// Create the normalization builder object
// (standard min/max normalization)
```

```

INormalizationBuilder normalizationBuilder
    = new StandardLinearBuilder();

// Create the normalization objects (one
// per each dimension)
25 INormalization[] normalizations =
    normalizationBuilder.getNormalizations(
        os);

System.out.println("The number of
    normalization objects = " +
        normalizations.length);
for (INormalization normalization :
    normalizations) System.out.println(
    normalization.toString());
System.out.println();

30 // Test data
double[][] testData = new double[][]
{
    {0.0d, 2.0d}, // utopia -> will map into
        0.0d and 0.0d
35 {0.25d, 2.5d}, // will map into 0.25d,
        0.25d
    {0.5d, 3.0d}, // will map into 0.5d, 0.5d
    {0.75d, 3.5d}, // will map into 0.75d,
        0.75d
    {1.0d, 4.0d}, // nadir -> will map into
        1.0d, 1.0d
40 {2.0d, 6.0d}, // outside the bounds ->
        will map into 2.0d, 2.0d
};

// Iterate and print normalization results
for (double[] v : testData)
45 {
    System.out.println("Case = " + PrintUtils
        .getVectorOfDoubles(v, 2));
    for (int n = 0; n < normalizations.length
        ; n++)
    {
        double normalized = normalizations[n].
            getNormalized(v[n]);
50 System.out.println("Normalization
            object #" + n + " mapped " + v[n] +
                " into " + normalized);
    }
}

```

Case #2.

Source package:
t1.t10.t13.evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.
t1_cases1.t1

This example differs from the previous one in terms of the criteria types. Specifically, the preference direction of the first objective is now maximization (hence, the value of 1 is the best and should be mapped into 0, while 0 is the worst and

```

Printing information on the objective space:
Utopia point = 0,0000 2,0000
Nadir point = 1,0000 4,0000
Ranges data:
Left = 0,0000; Right = 1,0000
Left = 2,0000; Right = 4,0000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization

The number of normalization objects = 2
Linear normalization: min = 0,000000; max = 1,000000
Linear normalization: min = 2,000000; max = 4,000000

Case = 0,00 2,00
Normalization object #0 mapped 0.0 into 0.0
Normalization object #1 mapped 2.0 into 0.0
Case = 0,25 2,50
Normalization object #0 mapped 0.25 into 0.25
Normalization object #1 mapped 2.5 into 0.25
Case = 0,50 3,00
Normalization object #0 mapped 0.5 into 0.5
Normalization object #1 mapped 3.0 into 0.5
Case = 0,75 3,50
Normalization object #0 mapped 0.75 into 0.75
Normalization object #1 mapped 3.5 into 0.75
Case = 1,00 4,00
Normalization object #0 mapped 1.0 into 1.0
Normalization object #1 mapped 4.0 into 1.0
Case = 2,00 6,00
Normalization object #0 mapped 2.0 into 2.0
Normalization object #1 mapped 6.0 into 2.0

```

Figure 2: The expected console output (Case #1)

should be mapped into 1). The input data points are now: [1, 2], [0.75, 2.5], [0.5, 3], [0.25, 3.5], [0, 4], [-1, 6], and they should be normalized as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 [1, 2] &\rightarrow [1 - (1 - 0) / (1 - 0) = 0, (2 - 2) / (4 - 2) = 0] \\
 [0.75, 2.5] &\rightarrow [1 - (0.75 - 0) / (1 - 0) = 0.25, (2.5 - 2) / (4 - 2) = 0.25] \\
 [0.5, 3] &\rightarrow [1 - (0.5 - 0) / (1 - 0) = 0.5, (3 - 2) / (4 - 2) = 0.5] \\
 [0.25, 3.5] &\rightarrow [1 - (0.25 - 0) / (1 - 0) = 0.75, (3.5 - 2) / (4 - 2) = 0.75] \\
 [0, 4] &\rightarrow [1 - (0 - 0) / (1 - 0) = 1, (5 - 2) / (4 - 2) = 1] \\
 [-1, 6] &\rightarrow [1 - (-1 - 0) / (1 - 0) = 2, (6 - 2) / (4 - 2) = 2]
 \end{aligned}$$

The source code of this example is in Listing 8, while the expected console output is illustrated in Figure 3 for convenience.

Listing 8: Case #2

```

// Create known ranges for the OS manager
// (each associated with a different
// dimension, 1:1 mapping).
// Dimension #1 = [0, 1]
// Dimension #2 = [2, 4]

```

```

Range[] ranges = new Range[]
5 {
    Range.getNormalRange(),
    new Range(2.0d, 4.0)
};

10 // Let's alter one of the criteria types:
boolean[] criteriaTypes = new boolean[]{
    true, false};
// Consequently the utopia point = [1, 2],
// while the nadir point = [0, 4].

ObjectiveSpace os = new ObjectiveSpace(
    ranges, criteriaTypes);

15 System.out.println("Printing information on
    the objective space:");
System.out.println(os);

INormalizationBuilder normalizationBuilder
    = new StandardLinearBuilder();

20 INormalization[] normalizations =
    normalizationBuilder.getNormalizations(
        os);

System.out.println("The number of
    normalization objects = " +
    normalizations.length);
for (INormalization normalization :
    normalizations) System.out.println(
    normalization.toString());
25 System.out.println();

// Test data
double[][] testData = new double[][]
{
30 {1.0d, 2.0d}, // utopia -> will map into
    0.0d and 0.0d
    {0.75d, 2.5d}, // will map into 0.25d,
    0.25d
    {0.5d, 3.0d}, // will map into 0.5d, 0.5d
    {0.25d, 3.5d}, // will map into 0.75d,
    0.75d
    {0.0d, 4.0d}, // nadir -> will map into
    1.0d, 1.0d
35 {-1.0d, 6.0d}, // outside the bounds ->
    will map into 2.0d, 2.0d
};

// Iterate and print normalization results
40 for (double[] v : testData)
{
    System.out.println("Case = " + PrintUtils
        .getVectorOfDoubles(v, 2));
    for (int n = 0; n < normalizations.length
        ; n++)
    {
45         double normalized = normalizations[n].
            getNormalized(v[n]);
        System.out.println("Normalization

```

```

        object #" + n + " mapped " + v[n] +
        " into " + normalized);
    }
}

```

```

Printing information on the objective space:
Utopia point = 1,0000 2,0000
Nadir point = 0,0000 4,0000
Ranges data:
Left = 0,0000; Right = 1,0000
Left = 2,0000; Right = 4,0000
Criteria types:
Maximization
Minimization

The number of normalization objects = 2
Min-Max with flip normalization: min = 0,000000; max = 1,000000; threshold = 1,000000
Linear normalization: min = 2,000000; max = 4,000000

Case = 1,00 2,00
Normalization object #0 mapped 1.0 into 0.0
Normalization object #1 mapped 2.0 into 0.0
Case = 0,75 2,50
Normalization object #0 mapped 0.75 into 0.25
Normalization object #1 mapped 2.5 into 0.25
Case = 0,50 3,00
Normalization object #0 mapped 0.5 into 0.5
Normalization object #1 mapped 3.0 into 0.5
Case = 0,25 3,50
Normalization object #0 mapped 0.25 into 0.75
Normalization object #1 mapped 3.5 into 0.75
Case = 0,00 4,00
Normalization object #0 mapped 0.0 into 1.0
Normalization object #1 mapped 4.0 into 1.0
Case = -1,00 6,00
Normalization object #0 mapped -1.0 into 2.0
Normalization object #1 mapped 6.0 into 2.0

```

Figure 3: The expected console output (Case #2)

2.2.5. Objective space manager

Updating the data on the objective space and constructing relevant normalization objects throughout the evolutionary process is automated by default in JECMD. Specifically, it is handled by the *ObjectiveSpaceManager* class (see *os* package), which plays a similar role to the *DisplayRangesManager* introduced for the *Visualization* module. It contains an “update” method that is supposed to be called anytime the known bounds on the objective space could change (e.g., after constructing new solutions). If such a change is indeed recorded, the manager notifies the listeners about this fact (passing the relevant data on the current objective space object). Naturally, the manager may be parameterized in various ways. Overall, four strategies regarding handling rescaling can be established:

- Not using rescaling: The objective space manager can be told to do nothing, and the rescaling-dependent components can be provided with no normalization objects. The default implementations will then perform such operations (e.g., calculating crowding distances in NSGA-II) using the original objective vectors. This strategy is highly not recommended.
- Providing no initial rescaling data but allowing this information to be dynamically updated throughout evolution: Such a scenario can test algorithms’ ability to adapt to constantly changing known bounds of the feasible objective space (or Pareto front).

- Providing initial data but turning off the dynamic update: This strategy can be considered the most reasonable one if the Pareto front's exact bounds are known in advance (but this is rarely the case). If so, there is no need to dynamically update the data on the objective space, securing stability in evolutionary search.
- Providing initial data and allowing for dynamic updates: This can be considered the most reasonable strategy in practical applications. In reality, one can first optimize each objective function individually to approximate the Pareto front bounds. A multi-objective optimizer can then be supplied with this approximation to ensure excellent starting conditions. Allowing it to dynamically update the bounds if even more promising solutions are created may further improve the final results.

The *ObjectiveSpaceManager.Params* class, provided in Listing 9, is designed to customize the processing of the *ObjectiveSpaceManager*. Let's delve into its fields and how they can be used to tailor the manager's behavior.

First, the “*doNotUpdateOS*” flag can be set to true to turn off the processing of the “*update*” method (which will also surpass the indications of other parameterization fields).

Next, the “*updateUtopiaUsingIncumbent*” and “*updateNadirUsingIncumbent*” can be suitably adjusted to establish various update strategies. These flags play a similar role to the “update from scratch” flag of the *DisplayRangesManager* class. If they are set to false, their respective points (utopia/nadir) are always determined “from scratch”, i.e., without looking at previous indications. In turn, setting them to true will ensure that the update procedure will involve the results from previous calls, and the current utopia/nadir points will be compared with stored incumbents (so the coordinate of the utopia can only monotonically improve, while the coordinates of the nadir deteriorate). For the standard implementations of methods for multi-objective optimization that perform rescaling based on the known bounds of the Pareto front, it is recommended to use the incumbent for the utopia point but not for the nadir. In turn, for preference-learning interactive methods, it is suggested to use incumbent for both to prevent pre-mature convergence into some highly sub-optimal point.

The following two fields are self-explanatory: “*criteria*” wraps all *Criteria* objects that are assumed to be associated 1:1 with the assumed objective functions, while the “*os*” can be set to provide initial data on the objective space bounds.

Listing 9: *ObjectiveSpaceManager.Params* class

```

/**
 * Params container.
 */
public static class Params
{
    [...]

    /**
     * If true, the update procedure will
     terminate immediately after being

```

```

        called. This flag can be used to
        surpass
    * updating data (e.g. when the OS is
      known in advance and is assumed to be
      fixed).
    */
public boolean _doNotUpdateOS = false;

/**
 * If true, objective space is updated
  based not only on the current
  population but the historical data as
  well (compare with the incumbent).
 */
public boolean
    _updateUtopiaUsingIncumbent = false;

/**
 * If true, objective space is updated
  based not only on the current
  population but the historical data as
  well (compare with the incumbent).
 */
public boolean _updateNadirUsingIncumbent
    = false;

/**
 * Considered criteria.
 */
public Criteria _criteria;

/**
 * Initial objective space object (can be
  null).
 */
public final ObjectiveSpace _os;

/**
 * Array of "objective space changed"
  listeners (can be null; will be set
  by a dedicated method in {@link ea.
  AbstractEABundle}).
 */
public IOSChangeListener[] _listeners =
    null;

[...]

/**
 * Provide specimens for analysis. If
  null, the {@link PopulationGetter}
  and {@link OffspringGetter} will be
  used.
 */
public ISpecimenGetter []
    _specimenGetters; = null;

[...]
}

```

Next, the “*listeners*” arrays can be instantiated and supplied with objects that will be notified each time the knowledge of the

objective space changes when running the main update method (see the *IOSChangeListener* interface brought in Listing 10). The developed algorithms may implement their listeners and couple them with the manager to receive data updates that are relevant for processing. Note that these listeners are typically not intended to be provided manually but should be created when instantiating the algorithm’s bundle (see the constructor of *AbstractEABundle* class and the *registerOSChangeListener* method that can be overwritten).

Listing 10: IOSChangeListener interface

```
public interface IOSChangeListener
{
    /**
     * Action to be performed when there is a
     * change in the objective space.
     * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
     * @param os objective space (updated)
     * @param prevOS previous objective
     * space (outdated; for comparison)
     * @throws PhaseException the exception
     * can be thrown and propagated higher
     */
    void action(EA ea, ObjectiveSpace os,
                ObjectiveSpace prevOS) throws
                PhaseException;
}
```

The last field is the “*specimenGetters*” vector. The stored objects implement an auxiliary *ISpecimenGetter* interface (see the code in Listing 11). Its implementations are designed to pass a relevant specimen array from the specimen container. Thus, this field allows for defining the sources for the input data used when updating the knowledge of the objective space bounds. If not provided, the manager will automatically utilize *PopulationGetter* and *OffspringGetter* (returns the population array and the offspring array from the specimen container; so both the current population and the offspring will contribute to determining the bounds).

Listing 11: ISpecimenGetter interface

```
/**
 * Simple interface for retrieving specimen
 * arrays form specimen container.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public interface ISpecimenGetter
{
    /**
     * Retrieves specimen array from the
     * container.
     *
     * @param container container
     * @return specimen array
     */
    ArrayList<Specimen> getSpecimens(
        SpecimensContainer container);
}
```

Finally, Listing 12 brings code snippets from the *ObjectiveSpaceManager* class focused on the constructor and the “*update*” method (its signature mostly) for the reader’s convenience.

Listing 12: ObjectiveSpaceManager class

```
public class ObjectiveSpaceManager
{
    [...]

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param p params container
     */
    public ObjectiveSpaceManager(Params p)
    {
        _doNotUpdateOS = p._doNotUpdateOS;
        _ea = p._ea;
        _criteria = p._criteria;
        _listeners = p._listeners;
        _os = p._os;
        _updateUtopiaUsingIncumbent = p.
            _updateUtopiaUsingIncumbent;
        _updateNadirUsingIncumbent = p.
            _updateNadirUsingIncumbent;
        _changed = false;
        _storeTimestamps = p._storeTimestamps;
        _specimenGetters = p._specimenGetters;
        if (_specimenGetters == null)
        {
            _specimenGetters = new
                ISpecimenGetter [2];
            _specimenGetters[0] = new
                PopulationGetter ();
            _specimenGetters[1] = new
                OffspringGetter ();
        }

        if (p._storeTimestamps)
            _notificationTimes = new LinkedList
                <>();
        else _notificationTimes = null;
    }

    [...]

    /**
     * Updates the knowledge on the objective
     * space.
     *
     * @param specimensContainer specimens
     * container maintained by the EA (e.g.,
     * current population, mating pool,
     * offspring)
     * @param timestamp current
     * generation no. and steady-state
     * repeat
     * @param notifyAboutChange if true, the
     * method accordingly updates the
     * _changed flag and triggers the
```

```

    listener
    * @return the method returns true if a
      change in OS is reported; false
      otherwise
    * @throws PhaseException the exception
      can be thrown and propagated higher
    */
45 public boolean update(SpecimensContainer
    specimensContainer, EATimestamp
    timestamp, boolean notifyAboutChange)
    throws PhaseException
    {
    if (!_doNotUpdateOS) return false;

    [...]

50 // notify the listeners about the
    change
    if ((_changed) && (_listeners != null))
    for (IOSChangeListener cl :
    _listeners) cl.action(_ea, os,
    previous);

55 return _changed;
    }
}

```

2.2.6. Example uses #2 [T]

This section presents a few examples of how the objective space manager can be parameterized and used. Note that, however, this class is not intended to be used explicitly, but it was developed to be part of an evolutionary algorithm that handles related processing. Therefore, this section introduces some “dummy” implementations allowing us to utilize the *ObjectiveSpaceManager* class independently of the *ea.EA*.

The first class implemented is a dummy *ISpecimenGetter*, named *DummyGetter* (see the *t3_evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.t1_cases2.common* package). It is a self-explanatory implementation that stores predefined specimen arrays and returns them cyclically when the “*getSpecimens*” method is called (see the code in Listing 13).

Listing 13: DummyGetter class

```

public class DummyGetter implements
    ISpecimenGetter
    {
    /**
    * Dummy specimens.
    */
    private final ArrayList<ArrayList<
    Specimen>> _dummySpecimens;

    /**
    * Current index.
    */
    private int _index = -1;

    /**

```

```

    * Parameterized constructor (uses one
      data set).
    *
    * @param performances performance matrix
    .
    */
    public DummyGetter(double [][]
    performances)
    {
    this(new double [][] [] {performances});
    }

    /**
    * Parameterized constructor (uses
      multiple data sets).
    *
    * @param performances performance matrix
      (multiple data sets).
    */
    public DummyGetter(double [][] []
    performances)
    {
    _dummySpecimens = new ArrayList<>(
    performances.length);
    for (double [][] pm : performances)
    {
    ArrayList<Specimen> specimens = new
    ArrayList<>(pm.length);
    for (double [] v : pm) specimens.add(
    new Specimen(v));
    _dummySpecimens.add(specimens);
    }
    }

    /**
    * Retrieves the dummy specimens array.
    *
    * @param container container
    * @return specimen array
    */
    @Override
    public ArrayList<Specimen> getSpecimens(
    SpecimensContainer container)
    {
    _index++;
    if (_index == _dummySpecimens.size())
    _index = 0;
    return _dummySpecimens.get(_index);
    }
}

```

Another auxiliary implementation is the *PrintingListener* class, which implements the *IOSChangeListener*. When the “*action*” method is called (triggered when some changes in the known objective space have been identified), it prints the string representation of the previous objective space (if not null) and the current one (see the code in Listing 14).

Listing 14: PrintingListener class

```

public class PrintingListener implements
    IOSChangeListener

```

```

{
  /**
   * Action to be performed when there is a
   *   change in the objective space.
5   *
   * @param ea      evolutionary algorithm
   * @param os      objective space (updated
   *   )
   * @param prevOS previous objective space
   *   (outdated; for comparison)
   * @throws PhaseException the exception
   *   can be thrown and propagated higher
10  */
  @Override
  public void action(EA ea, ObjectiveSpace
    os, ObjectiveSpace prevOS) throws
    PhaseException
  {
    System.out.println("Printing listener
      action triggered:");
15    System.out.println("Previous objective
      space:");
    if (prevOS != null) prevOS.print();
    else System.out.println("None");
    System.out.println("Current objective
      space:");
    if (os != null) os.print();
    else System.out.println("None");
20  }
}

```

as follows:

```

[-0.5,0.5]
[1.5, - 1.5]
[0.9,0.9]

[-0.5,0.5]
[1.5, - 1.5]
[0.9,0.9]

[-2.5,0.5]
[2.5, - 4.5]
[1.0,0.0].

```

The source code of this tutorial is presented in Listing 15 for convenience. Given the above configuration, the expected states after each update are as follows:

1. The performance values are in $[-0.5, 1.5]$ (first objective) and $[-1.5, 0.9]$ (second objective) bounds. However, the initial bounds of $[0, 1]$ for both objectives are given, and the comparison involves incumbent utopia/nadir points. Therefore, the expected bounds are $[-0.5, 1.5]$ and $[-1.5, 1.0]$ ($0.9 \rightarrow 1.0$).
2. The second performance matrix is identical to the first one. Therefore, no changes will be detected, and thus, the listener's action will not be triggered.
3. The third update will extend the known bounds to $[-2.5, 2.5]$ and $[-4.5, 1.0]$.

The expected console output is illustrated in Figure 4.

Case #1.

```

Source package:
t1_t10.t3_evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.
t2_osmanager.t1

```

This tutorial example makes the following assumptions:

- The number of objectives is 2, and both are to be minimized.
- The initial data on the objective space bounds is specified: $[0, 1]$ for both objectives.
- The updates will involve the utopia/nadir incumbent points.
- There will be three calls of the update method, and the dummy performance matrices used in *DummyGetter* are

Listing 15: Case #1

```

// Create default OS (2 dimensions, [0-1]
//   ranges, objectives to be minimized):
ObjectiveSpace os = new ObjectiveSpace(
  Range.getDefaultRanges(2), new boolean
  [2]);

// Create OS Params container:
ObjectiveSpaceManager.Params pOSM = new
  ObjectiveSpaceManager.Params(os);
// Define criteria:
pOSM._criteria = Criteria.constructCriteria
  ("C", 2, false);
// Update both points using an incumbent:
pOSM._updateUtopiaUsingIncumbent = true;
pOSM._updateNadirUsingIncumbent = true;

// Create dummy getter:
pOSM._specimenGetters = new ISpecimenGetter
  []{
  new DummyGetter(new double[][][]{
15    {
      {-0.5d, 0.5d},
      {1.5d, -1.5d},
      {0.9d, 0.9d}
    }
  }
}

```

```

    },
    { // no change
      {-0.5d, 0.5d},
      {1.5d, -1.5d},
      {0.9d, 0.9d}
    },
    {
      {-2.5d, 0.5d},
      {2.5d, -4.5d},
      {1.0d, 0.0d}
    }
  })
};

// Create printing listener:
pOSM._listeners = new IOSChangeListener[] {
  new PrintingListener()};

// Create OS manager:
ObjectiveSpaceManager OSM = new
  ObjectiveSpaceManager(pOSM);

try
{
  System.out.println("Update no. 1
=====
===");
  // Specimens container must be provided (
  even if empty):
  OSM.update(new SpecimensContainer(), null
  );
  System.out.println("Update no. 2
=====
===");
  OSM.update(new SpecimensContainer(), null
  );

} catch (PhaseException e)
{
  throw new RuntimeException(e);
}

```

```

Update no. 1 =====
Printing listener action triggered:
Previous objective space:
Utopia point = 0,000000000000000 0,000000000000000
Nadir point = 1,000000000000000 1,000000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = 0,000000000000000; Right = 1,000000000000000
Left = 0,000000000000000; Right = 1,000000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
Current objective space:
Utopia point = -0,500000000000000 -1,500000000000000
Nadir point = 1,500000000000000 1,000000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = -0,500000000000000; Right = 1,500000000000000
Left = -1,500000000000000; Right = 1,000000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
Update no. 2 =====
Update no. 3 =====
Printing listener action triggered:
Previous objective space:
Utopia point = -0,500000000000000 -1,500000000000000
Nadir point = 1,500000000000000 1,000000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = -0,500000000000000; Right = 1,500000000000000
Left = -1,500000000000000; Right = 1,000000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
Current objective space:
Utopia point = -2,500000000000000 -4,500000000000000
Nadir point = 2,500000000000000 1,000000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = -2,500000000000000; Right = 2,500000000000000
Left = -4,500000000000000; Right = 1,000000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization

```

Case #2.

Source package:
t1_t10.t3_evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.
t2_osmanager.t2

This case differs from the previous one in the following:

- It does not provide the initial objective space data.
- The utopia/nadir incumbent points are not involved in the updates.
- There will be two calls of the update method with the fol-

Figure 4: The expected console output (Case #1)

lowing data:

- [-0.5,0.5]
- [1.5, - 1.5]
- [1.0,1.0]
- [0.5,0.5]
- [0.25, - 4.5]
- [0.75,0.0].

The expected results are as follows:

1. The bounds determined after the first update are $[-0.5, 1.5]$ and $[-1.5, 1.0]$.
2. The second update does not use past data (utopia/nadir points). Hence, the newly formed bounds should be $[0.25, 0.75]$ and $[-4.5, 0.5]$.

The expected console output is illustrated in Figure 5.

```
Update no. 1 =====
Printing listener action triggered:
Previous objective space:
None
Current objective space:
Utopia point = -0,5000000000000000 -1,5000000000000000
Nadir point = 1,5000000000000000 1,0000000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = -0,5000000000000000; Right = 1,5000000000000000
Left = -1,5000000000000000; Right = 1,0000000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
Update no. 2 =====
Printing listener action triggered:
Previous objective space:
Utopia point = -0,5000000000000000 -1,5000000000000000
Nadir point = 1,5000000000000000 1,0000000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = -0,5000000000000000; Right = 1,5000000000000000
Left = -1,5000000000000000; Right = 1,0000000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
Current objective space:
Utopia point = 0,2500000000000000 -4,5000000000000000
Nadir point = 0,7500000000000000 0,5000000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = 0,2500000000000000; Right = 0,7500000000000000
Left = -4,5000000000000000; Right = 0,5000000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
```

Figure 5: The expected console output (Case #2)

Case #3.

```
Source package:
t1.t10.t3_evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.
t2_osmanager.t3
```

The last case shows that adjusting the incumbent-related flags can establish various update strategies. Specifically, the nadir-related incumbent is not used in this example, while the utopia

one is. The input data for the two updates to be conducted is:

- $[2.0, 0.0]$
- $[0.0, 0.0]$
- $[0.0, 2.0]$
- $[0.5, 0.1]$
- $[0.25, 0.25]$
- $[0.1, 0.5]$.

Therefore, the expected bounds after each update call are as follows:

- The bounds should be $[0, 2]$ and $[0, 2]$ for the first update.
- After the second update, the bounds should be $[0.0, 0.5]$ and $[0.0, 0.5]$. Note that the utopia point did not deteriorate to $[0.1, 0.1]$ because the comparison used the incumbent point. Regarding the nadir point, only the current data was employed in calculations (hence, the nadir moved from $[2.0, 2.0]$ to $[0.5, 0.5]$).

Figure 6 illustrates the expected console output.

2.2.7. Update objective phase

This section presents the default “update objective space” phase implemented for JECDM (see *phase* package). It was already introduced in the first part of the tutorial document on the *EvolutionaryComputation* module, but it is brought here for the reader’s convenience. The phase’s main action is in Listing 16. Notably, the procedure is straightforward, and it delegates the determination of the objective space bounds to the *ObjectiveSpaceManager* object.

Listing 16: UpdateObjectiveSpace class (action method)

```
/**
 * Phase main action (calls for update of
 * the objective space manager).
 *
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param report report on the executed
 * action (to be filled)
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 * be thrown and propagated higher
 */
@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
    report) throws PhaseException
{
    _osManager.update(ea.
        getSpecimensContainer(), new
        EATimestamp(ea.getCurrentGeneration(),
            ea.getCurrentSteadyStateRepeat()));
}
```

In general, the simplified processing flow illustrated in Figure 1, can now be described as follows:

```

Update no. 1 =====
Printing listener action triggered:
Previous objective space:
None
Current objective space:
Utopia point = 0,000000000000000 0,000000000000000
Nadir point = 2,000000000000000 2,000000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = 0,000000000000000; Right = 2,000000000000000
Left = 0,000000000000000; Right = 2,000000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
Update no. 2 =====
Printing listener action triggered:
Previous objective space:
Utopia point = 0,000000000000000 0,000000000000000
Nadir point = 2,000000000000000 2,000000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = 0,000000000000000; Right = 2,000000000000000
Left = 0,000000000000000; Right = 2,000000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization
Current objective space:
Utopia point = 0,000000000000000 0,000000000000000
Nadir point = 0,500000000000000 0,500000000000000
Ranges data:
Left = 0,000000000000000; Right = 0,500000000000000
Left = 0,000000000000000; Right = 0,500000000000000
Criteria types:
Minimization
Minimization

```

Figure 6: The expected console output (Case #3)

1. The “update objective space” phase is executed (*action* method). By default, it is executed just after new specimens are created, evaluated, and assigned IDs.
2. The phase delegates the calculation of objective space bounds to the objective space manager object (update method).
3. The objective space manager determines the bounds based on specimen arrays delivered via *ISpecimenGetter* objects (current population and offspring, by default).
4. If the known bounds differ between subsequent method calls (changed), the data on the current (and past) objective space is passed via registered listeners (*IOSChangeListener*s) to interested receives (who may then, for instance, use an *INormalizationBuilder* object to construct relevant normalization procedures used in rescaling-dependent calculations, e.g., computing crowding-distances).

2.3. Multi-objective optimization problem bundle

The problem bundle classes were introduced to help organize consistent, problem-related entities. As explained in the pre-

vious tutorial document, the *AbstractProblemBundle* class was introduced mainly to wrap three parts of the evolutionary algorithm processing: constructing initial specimens (*IConstruct* interface), reproducing specimens (*IReproduce* interface), and evaluating specimens (*IEvaluate* interface). The implementations of these three interfaces should be consistent when wrapped in a single bundle. That means they should assume the exact solution representation and the same fields used to store/retrieve relevant data (i.e., decision vectors).

In the context of multi-objective optimization, an extension of the default *AbstractProblemBundle* class is introduced: *AbstractMOOPProblemBundle* (see *problem.moo* package). It introduces new fields that may be helpful when tuning the optimizer or analyzing the method’s performance. They are automatically set by predefined problem bundle constructors, but this will be covered later in this section.

The *AbstractMOOPProblemBundle* class is brought in Listing 17 for convenience. Let’s look at its fields. First, the “*_displayRanges*” vector can be instantiated with the objective space bounds that could be employed in the visualization module to focus the rendering on the most relevant part of this space. Note that these bounds may not necessarily match the problem’s true utopia and nadir points. The latter point may be slightly extended (outwards the utopia) to allow observing how the population of solutions converges to the Pareto front during the evolutionary search. It is also implicitly assumed that each element vector corresponds 1:1 (by index) with each assumed objective function.

Next, a bundle constructor may specify the “*_paretoFrontBounds*” field that is supposed to store the data on the objective bounds on which the whole Pareto front is spanned. Then, the “*_normalizations*” field can be utilized to provide predefined normalization functions that correctly map the objective vectors that are between the utopia and nadir points into the standard $[0, 1]^M$ hypercube. Then, the “*_utopia*” and “*_nadir*” points can be supplied. Further, the “*_optimizationDirections*” vector can be employed to specify which objectives are to be maximized (“true” flags) and which are to be minimized (“false” flags). Lastly, “*_criteria*” can be utilized to provide reference criteria container.

Listing 17: AbstractMOOPProblemBundle class

```

/**
 * Abstract bundle (container) for default
 * implementations of problem-related
 * phases (construct/reproduce/evaluate,
 * etc.)
 * and OS-related data helpful when solving
 * various MOO problems.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public abstract class
AbstractMOOPProblemBundle extends
AbstractProblemBundle
{
/**
 * Display ranges for test problems used

```

```

        when performing visualization (they
        may not match the true utopia/nadir
        points).
    */
    public final Range[] _displayRanges;

    /**
    * Bounds for the Pareto front.
    */
    public final Range[] _paretoFrontBounds;

    /**
    * Min-max normalizations for test
    * problems (min = true utopia point,
    * max = true nadir point).
    */
    public final INormalization[]
        _normalizations;

    /**
    * True utopia for test problems.
    */
    public final double[] _utopia;

    /**
    * True utopia for test problems.
    */
    public final double[] _nadir;

    /**
    * Optimization direction flags (for each
    * objective). True indicates that the
    * objective is to be maximized, false
    * otherwise.
    */
    public final boolean[]
        _optimizationDirections;

    /**
    * Contains reference criteria objects.
    */
    public final Criteria _criteria;

    /**
    * Parameterized constructor.
    *
    * @param problem          problem
    *                          id
    * @param construct       constructs the initial population
    * @param reproduce       creates
    *                          offspring
    * @param evaluate        Evaluates solutions
    * @param displayRanges   display
    *                          ranges for a test problem used when
    *                          performing visualization (they may
    *                          not match the true utopia/nadir
    *                          points)
    * @param paretoFrontBounds  bounds
    *                          for the Pareto front
    * @param normalizations  min-max

```

```

        normalizations for a test problem (
        min = true utopia point, max = true
        nadir point)
    * @param utopia          true
    *                          utopia point for a test problem
    * @param nadir          true
    *                          nadir point for a test problem
    * @param optimizationDirections
    *                          optimization direction flags (for
    *                          each objective); true indicates that
    *                          the objective is to be maximized,
    *                          false otherwise
    * @param criteria        default
    *                          criteria definitions
    */
    protected AbstractMOOProblemBundle(
        Problem problem, IConstruct construct,
        IReproduce reproduce, IEvaluate
        evaluate, Range[] displayRanges, Range
        [] paretoFrontBounds, INormalization[]
        normalizations, double[] utopia,
        double[] nadir, boolean[]
        optimizationDirections, Criteria
        criteria)
    {
        super(problem, construct, reproduce,
            evaluate);
        _displayRanges = displayRanges;
        _paretoFrontBounds = paretoFrontBounds;
        _normalizations = normalizations;
        _utopia = utopia;
        _nadir = nadir;
        _optimizationDirections =
            optimizationDirections;
        _criteria = criteria;
    }

    [...]
}

```

The *AbstractMOOProblemBundle* is intended to be extended to introduce means for automatically creating data for concrete benchmarks. In the initial version of JECMDM, two such extensions are provided: *DTLZBundle* (*problem.moo.dtlz* package) and *WFGBundle* (*problem.moo.wfg* package). Of course, these refer to the two well-known test suites in multi-objective optimization: DTLZ [2] and WFG [3]. The design of these bundle classes is similar. Hence, we will focus on the *DTLZBundle* in what follows for brevity.

The *DTLZBundle* class has a static “*getBundle*” method that allows retrieving a suitably parameterized DTLZ bundle (see Listing 18). Notably, it accepts three inputs: problem (problem identifier), M – the number of objectives, and D – the number of distance-related variables. Then, the method fills bundle’s fields using dedicated procedures (e.g., “*displayRanges = getDisplayRanges()*”). These procedures return data that match the problem’s properties (e.g., the Pareto front bounds for the DTLZ2 test problem are $[0, 1]^M$).

Listing 18: DTLZBundle class (getBundle method)

```

/**
 * Getter for the default bundle for DTLZ
 * problems.
 *
 * @param problem problem id
 * @param M the number of considered
 * objectives
 * @param D the number of distance-related
 * variables
 * @return bundle
 */
public static DTLZBundle getBundle(Problem
    problem, int M, int D)
{
    IConstruct construct = new Construct(M, D
    );
    IEvaluate evaluate;
    switch (problem)
    {
        case DTLZ2 -> evaluate = new DTLZ2(M, D
        );
        case DTLZ3 -> evaluate = new DTLZ3(M, D
        );
        case DTLZ4 -> evaluate = new DTLZ4(M, D
        );
        case DTLZ5 -> evaluate = new DTLZ5(M, D
        );
        case DTLZ6 -> evaluate = new DTLZ6(M, D
        );
        case DTLZ7 -> evaluate = new DTLZ7(M, D
        );
        default -> evaluate = new DTLZ1(M, D);
    }
    ICrossover crossover = new SBX(new SBX.
        Params(1.0d, 20.0d));
    IMutate mutate = new PM(new PM.Params(1.0
        d / ((double) D + M - 1), 20.0d));
    IReproduce reproduce = new Reproduce(M, D
    , crossover, mutate);
    Range[] displayRanges = getDisplayRanges(
    problem, M);
    Range[] paretoFrontBounds =
        getParetoFrontBounds(problem, M);
    INormalization[] normalizations =
        getNormalizations(problem, M);
    double[] utopia = getUtopia(problem, M);
    double[] nadir = getnadir(problem, M);
    return new DTLZBundle(problem, construct,
        reproduce, evaluate, displayRanges,
        paretoFrontBounds, normalizations,
        utopia, nadir, new boolean[M],
        Criteria.constructCriteria("C", M, false)
    );
}

```

Apart from the data related to the properties of the objective space, the method instantiates the *IConstruct*, *IEvaluate*, and *IReproduce* objects. These are ready-to-use implementations that can be used off-the-shelf. Nonetheless, one can prepare their own implementations and supply them to the bundle. These implementations may introduce, e.g., an entirely dif-

ferent specimen representation or use other reproduction techniques. The default implementations prepared for this bundle use a straightforward, direct solution representation (i.e., the chromosome is a double decision vector to the DTLZ problem; the number of decision variables is $M - 1 + D$, as imposed by the problem definition), SBX and PM operators are used in the reproduction step, while the evaluator accepts the specimen's chromosome as the decision vector and uses it to evaluate the objective functions as imposed by the selected DTLZ problem (different evaluator is used for different problems).

Listings 19, 20, 21, and 22 present DTLZ default *IConstruct* implementation, *IReproduce* implementation, and two classes that jointly are responsible for evaluating an example DTLZ test problem – DTLZ1. They are brought here for the reader's convenience. All of them are relatively straightforward and, hence, do not need extensive elaboration. E.g., the constructor class (Listing 19) just creates specimens supplied with double decision vectors of size $M - 1 + D$ (variable values are bounded to $[0, 1]$ interval). The reproducer class (Listing 20) executes a standard crossover to construct the offspring's decision vector and perturbs it using a mutation operator (the default operators impose $[0, 1]$ bounds on variable values). Finally, an abstract *DTLZEvaluate* class is introduced (Listing 21) to introduce code generalization. Its instantiable extensions are just overwriting a function that implements the *decision vector* \rightarrow *objective vector* mapping (see Listing 22).

Listing 19: Construct class (dedicated to all DTLZ problems)

```

/**
 * Constructs random solutions for DTLZ
 * problems.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class Construct implements
    IConstruct
{
    /**
     * The number of position-related
     * variables (the number of objectives =
     * _P + 1).
     */
    protected final int _P;

    /**
     * The number of distance-related
     * variables.
     */
    protected final int _D;

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     * @param M the number of objectives
     * @param D the number of distance-
     * related parameters
     */
    public Construct(int M, int D)
    {
        _P = M - 1;
    }
}

```

```

    _D = D;
}

/**
 * Creates initial population randomly.
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @return initial population
 */
@Override
public ArrayList<Specimen>
    createInitialPopulation(EA ea)
{
    ArrayList<Specimen> S = new ArrayList
        <>(ea.getPopulationSize());
    int criteria = ea.getCriteria()._no;

    for (int s = 0; s < ea.
        getPopulationSize(); s++)
    {
        Specimen specimen = new Specimen(
            criteria);
        double[] x = new double[_P + _D];
        for (int i = 0; i < _P; i++) x[i] =
            ea.getRNG().nextDouble();
        for (int i = _P; i < _P + _D; i++) x[
            i] = ea.getRNG().nextDouble();
        specimen.setChromosome(new Chromosome
            (x));
        S.add(specimen);
    }
    return S;
}
}

```

Listing 20: Reproduce class (dedicated to all DTLZ problems)

```

/**
 * Creates offspring for the DTLZ problem (
 * default implementation).
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class Reproduce extends
    AbstractReproduce implements IReproduce
{
    /**
     * The number of position-related
     * variables (the number of objectives =
     * _P + 1)
     */
    protected final int _P;

    /**
     * The number of distance-related
     * variables.
     */
    protected final int _D;

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.

```

```

 *
 * @param M          the number of
 *                   objectives
 * @param D          the number of
 *                   distance-related parameters
 * @param crossover  crossover operator.
 * @param mutate     mutation operator.
 */
public Reproduce(int M, int D, ICrossover
    crossover, IMutate mutate)
{
    super(crossover, mutate, M);
    _P = M - 1;
    _D = D;
}

/**
 * Supportive method for constructing one
 * offspring.
 *
 * @param parents  parents array
 * @param R        random number generator
 * @return         constructed offspring
 */
@Override
protected Specimen createOffspring(
    ArrayList<Specimen> parents, IRandom R
    )
{
    double[] p1 = parents.get(0).
        getDoubleDecisionVector();
    double[] p2 = parents.get(1).
        getDoubleDecisionVector();
    double[] o = _crossover.crossover(p1,
        p2, R);
    _mutate.mutate(o, R);
    Chromosome c = new Chromosome(o);
    Specimen S = new Specimen(_criteria);
    S.setChromosome(c);
    return S;
}
}

```

Listing 21: DTLZEvaluate class (“evaluateSpecimens” and “evaluate” methods; dedicated to all DTLZ problems)

```

/**
 * Evaluates specimens.
 *
 * @param specimens array of specimens to
 *                   be evaluated
 */
@Override
public void evaluateSpecimens(ArrayList<
    Specimen> specimens)
{
    for (Specimen specimen : specimens)
    {
        double[] x = specimen.
            getDoubleDecisionVector();
        double[] f = evaluate(x);
        specimen.setEvaluations(f);

```

```

15 }
}

/**
 * Supportive method for calculating the
   objective vector.
 *
 * @param x decision vector
 * @return objective vector
 */
protected double [] evaluate(double [] x)
{
25     return null;
}

```

Listing 22: DTLZ1 class (“evaluate” method, dedicated to DTLZ1 problem)

```

/**
 * Supportive method for calculating
   objective vector.
 * @param x decision vector
 * @return objective vector
 */
@Override
protected double [] evaluate(double [] x)
{
    double g = 0.0;
    for (int i = _P; i < _P + _D; i++)
        g += (Math.pow(x[i] - 0.5d, 2.0d) -
              Math.cos(20.0d * Math.PI * (x[i] -
              0.5d)));
    g = 100.0d * (_D + g);

    double [] f = new double[_P + 1];

    for (int i = 0; i < _P + 1; i++)
    {
        f[i] = 0.5 * (1.0 + g);
        for (int j = 0; j < (_P + 1) - i - 1; j
            ++) f[i] *= x[j];
        if (i != 0) f[i] *= (1 - x[( _P + 1) - i
            - 1]);
    }
    return f;
}

```

2.4. Decomposition-related components

This section introduces and discusses the essential components that are employed by implemented decomposition-based methods (e.g., MOEA/D [4] or NSGA-III [5]). Note that it is not intended to discuss all functionalities they implement as most of the code is relatively self-explanatory, and getting acquainted with it is, therefore, left to the reader (programmer). Instead, this section delivers a general overview that should give an overall understanding of how the decomposition-based methods are implemented in JECDM. Also, it provides a good starting point in case one would like to implement one’s decomposition-based implementation of an evolutionary algorithm.

First, let us discuss the fundamental classes and their hierarchy, depicted in Figure 7. At the top, there is a “goals manager” object, which is an instantiable extension of an *AbstractGoalsManager* class (see *emo.utils.decomposition* package). It is a top-level component that handles all decomposition-related functionalities. It is supposed to be contained in an evolutionary algorithm that may employ the manager to drive the optimization process suitably. Next, the goals manager can maintain a series of “goals families” (see *emo.utils.decomposition.family* package). Each family is supposed to contain a set of so-called optimization goals (e.g., scalarizing functions) that are of the same form (but may be parameterized differently). For instance, one may parameterize the manager to contain two families: one formed of the weighted sum functions and the other of weighted Chebyshev functions. Note that the classic decomposition-based methods mentioned above employ just one family. More can be used, e.g., if the algorithm implements the concept of a co-evolution (e.g., CIEMO/D method [6]).

Each family consists of a series of optimization goals modeled using two entities: “goal wrapper” and “assignment” (see the *emo.utils.decomposition.goal* package). The first is a simple wrapper for an object implementing the *IGoal* interface, representing an optimization goal that can be employed to orient the search in the decomposition-based environment. The former object represents the goal↔specimen(s) assignments. For instance, MOEA/D assumes that one specimen can be assigned to multiple goals (but not vice-versa). Hence, the same specimen can be contained in multiple assignments, but one assignment can contain just one specimen. In turn, NSGA-III assumes the inverse relation. Thus, one assignment may contain multiple specimens, but the same specimen cannot be involved in different assignments. Overall, these classes provide just very general methods that concrete implementations of algorithms can suitably utilize to realize desired mappings.

Figure 7: Class hierarchy of the decomposition-related components

In what follows, the most essential classes are discussed, starting from the bottom of the class hierarchy and ending at the top.

2.4.1. Optimization goal

The *IGoal* (*emo.utils.decomposition.goal* package) is a straightforward interface introduced to establish a basic contract defin-

ing how an optimization goal should be utilized by, e.g., the goals manager (see the code in Listing 23). Its methods' definitions are self-explanatory. First, the “*evaluate*” method is supposed to assess the specimen's quality (returns double score). Next, the “*isLessPreferred*” method indicates the preference direction (“true” means that smaller values are preferred). Then, the “*updateNormalizations*” method can be used to pass the reference to normalization objects (constructed, e.g., automatically during the “update objective space” phase). The concrete implementation can then use these normalizations to rescale objective vectors suitably. Finally, “*getParams*” returns the goal's parameterization expressed as a two-dimensional matrix. Note that the interpretation of the returned values is dependent on implementation. This method is also used only occasionally. For instance, the JECMD implementation of the MOEA/D algorithm uses it when calculating similarities between goals (to construct the neighborhood structures).

Listing 23: IGoal interface

```

/**
 * Representation of a scalarized
 * optimization function (optimization
 * goal).
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public interface IGoal
{
    /**
     * Can be used to evaluate a specimen.
     *
     * @param specimen specimen object
     * @return specimen score
     */
    double evaluate(Specimen specimen);

    /**
     * Used to determine preference direction
     * (i.e., whether the smaller or bigger
     * values are preferred).
     * @return true -> smaller values are
     * preferred; false otherwise.
     */
    boolean isLessPreferred();

    /**
     * Can be called to update normalizations
     * used to rescale specimen evaluations
     *
     * @param normalizations normalization
     * functions (one per objective)
     */
    void updateNormalizations(INormalization
    [] normalizations);

    /**
     * Implementation specific getter for
     * data that can be used, e.g., to
     * quantify the similarity between goals

```

```

    *
    * @return data
    */
    double [][] getParams();
}

```

Goal definitions. The default goal definitions can be found in the *emo.utils.decomposition.goal.definitions* package. It is left to the reader to become acquainted with these classes (the implementations are straightforward). In a nutshell, an *AbstractGoal* is introduced to generalize the normalization-related processing. Then, it is extended by the *AbstractScalarGoal* class that is a wrapper for objects implementing the *IScalarFunction* interface (see the *space.scalarfunction* package in the *Utils* module). As the name suggests, the instantiable extensions of this class are intended to represent a scalarizing function, e.g., a weighted sum method. The default implementations introduced in the initial release of JECMD are *LNorm* (models the L_α^w -norm), *PBI* (models the penalty boundary intersection function), and *PointLineProjection* (models a function that calculates an orthogonal distance from a point to a line – used, e.g., in NSGA-III).

Goals factory. It is recommended to examine the *emo.utils.decomposition.goal.GoalsFactory* class that provides various static methods for creating a series of goals – of the same type – with uniformly distributed direction-related parameters. The default implementations for the initial release of JECMD use Das and Dennis' systematic approach [7] to generate the direction-related parameters (e.g., weights for L_α^w -norms). Then, they create and return parameterized object instances in this way. Such generated optimization goals may be used as input for, e.g., the MOEA/D method.

2.4.2. Assignment

Let us now look at the “*Assignment*” class (*emo.utils.decomposition.goal* package). Its purpose is to model a linkage between a goal and selected solutions. Its code is provided in Listing 24 but focuses only on the fields. It is up to the reader to check the available methods.

First, the assignment keeps the reference to the associated goal (each goal object is linked with one assignment object). Then, multiple specimens can be involved in one assignment and stored in the “*_specimens*” list. The motivation to use a list is to allow for keeping the specimens – of an unknown but rather small number – sorted according to their relevance to the goal. These relevance scores are kept in the complementary “*_evaluations*” list. For instance, the NSGA-III algorithm assigns specimens to their closest goals. Hence, a goal may be assigned to multiple specimens. Ultimately, however, only the best (or the bests) such specimens may have a chance to be employed in the population to be passed to the next iteration. To facilitate this process, the specimens and their evaluations are stored in lists, and the *Assignment* class provides useful methods for inserting specimens (and their relevance scores) in the insertion-sort-manner (keeping entries in both lists sorted; see

the “*insertSpecimen*” method). Finally, the “*_nicheCount*” field can be utilized to associate a niche count value associated with the goal (also used by NSGA-III).

Listing 24: Assignment class

```

/**
 * Represents the linkage goal &lt;!--&gt;
 * assigned specimens (e.g., in MOEA/D,
 * each goal is assigned exactly one
 * specimen;
 * but in NSGA-III the mapping is reversed)
 * . Specimens (and their evaluations) are
 * kept stored using lists. The class
 * provides various functionalities that
 * can be adapted by different algorithms.
 * For instance, the method allows
 * inserting new elements into the list
 * using the insertion sort procedure.
 * This way, the specimens can be kept
 * sorted
 * from the best to worst, given their
 * evaluations (used, e.g., in NSGA-II).
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class Assignment
{
    /**
     * Reference to the goal.
     */
    private final IGoal _goal;

    /**
     * Reference to the assigned specimens.
     */
    private final LinkedList<Specimen>
        _specimens;

    /**
     * Keeps evaluations of specimens that
     * are stored in the specimens lists.
     */
    private final LinkedList<Double>
        _evaluations;

    /**
     * Auxiliary field that can reflect niche
     * count of the goal’s surroundings.
     */
    protected double _nicheCount = 0.0f;

    [...]
}

```

2.4.3. Goals family

The goals (wrapped using *GoalWrapper*) and their linked assignments are kept in a “*Family*” object. Listing 25 presents the simple *Family* class, focusing only on its fields.

First, the “*_id*” field stores essential data uniquely identifying a given family (note that there is a similar *GoalID* class that is an identifier to goals). Next, the “*_goals*” array keeps the family’s goals, while the “*_assignments*” array keeps their assignments (the elements of both arrays are assumed to be connected 1:1, i.e., the *i*-th goal is associated with the *i*-th assignment).

Listing 25: Family class

```

/**
 * Class representing a family of goals.
 * Goals are stored in an array (in
 * wrappers), and it is assumed that the
 * array index is equivalent to goal id.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class Family
{
    /**
     * Family ID.
     */
    private final FamilyID _id;

    /**
     * Family’s optimization goals (wrapped;
     * array index is equivalent to goal id)
     * .
     */
    private GoalWrapper[] _goals;

    /**
     * Goals assignments data (i:i linkage
     * between this array and the _goals
     * array).
     */
    private Assignment[] _assignments;

    [...]
}

```

2.4.4. Goals manager

The *AbstractGoalsmanager* is at the top of the class hierarchy and is supposed to handle all the goal families and provide related (and) basic functionalities. It can be extended to introduce new, algorithm-dependent methods and adjust the processing. The most relevant code snippets of the abstract class are provided in Listing 26.

First, the object instance must be parameterized via the params container. Its major field used to tune the manager is the “*_goals*” matrix that determines the composition of employed families (each row contains goals for one family). The protected constructor of the *AbstractGoalsmanager* class employs these goals to instantiate the “*F*” (families) field.

The default implementations assume that the population size for the decomposition-based methods equals the total number of maintained goals. Hence, one element of the specimen array should have been connected with one goal (naturally, custom implementations may bypass/ignore

this assumption). Consequently, an additional field called “*_goalToSpecimenArrayIndex*” is introduced for convenience. It defines (by default) the (family/goal) → (specimen index in the population array) mapping. Note that the constructor calls the relevant “*_instantiateGoalToSpecimenArrayIndex*” method that can be overwritten in custom implementations. The default one iterates over all families and their goals and incrementally assigns an index, starting from zero. For instance, assume that there are two families, each with two goals. The constructed mapping would then take the following form: 0,1,2,3 (i.e., the first/second vector is associated with the first/second family, the array indices are associated with subsequent family’s goals, while the numbers represent the linked specimen array indices; hence the population size is assumed to be 4).

Lastly, consider the “*_updateNormalizations*” method. It can be called to pass (update) new normalization objects to all involved goals. This may be triggered by a *IOSChangeListener* object during the “*update objective space*” default phase in decomposition-based implementations.

Listing 26: AbstractGoalsManager class

```

/**
 * Abstract class providing various
 * functionalities for maintaining/
 * processing goals/assignments in a
 * decomposition-based
 * algorithm (primarily MOEA/D, but it can
 * be suitably adapted to various other
 * algorithmic purposes).
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
protected abstract class
    AbstractGoalsManager
{
    /**
     * Params container.
     */
    public static class Params
    {
        /**
         * Optimization goals (matrix: each
         * entry is a separate family).
         */
        public IGoal [][] _goals;

        [...]
    }

    /**
     * Goals families (is there is more than
     * one, the method can, e.g., be run in
     * a co-evolutionary mode).
     */
    protected final Family [] _F;

    /**
     * Represents mapping (family/goal) -> (
     * population) specimen array index. The
     * default implementations implicitly
     * assume that one goal should correspond
     * to one population member. This
     * abstract class instantiates this
     * linkage
     * by iterating over all families and
     * their goals and incrementally
     * assigning subsequent indices,
     * starting from 0.
     */
    protected int [][]
        _goalToSpecimenArrayIndex;

    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param p params container
     */
    protected AbstractGoalsManager(Params p)
    {
        _F = new Family[p._goals.length];
        for (int f = 0; f < p._goals.length; f
            ++){
            _F[f] = new Family(new FamilyID(f), p
                ._goals[f]);
            instantiateGoalToSpecimenArrayIndex(p);
        }

        /**
         * Auxiliary method for instantiating {
         * @link AbstractGoalsManager#
         * _goalToSpecimenArrayIndex}.
         *
         * @param p params container
         */
        protected void
            instantiateGoalToSpecimenArrayIndex(
                Params p)
        {
            _goalToSpecimenArrayIndex = new int[_F.
                length][];
            int arrayID = 0;
            for (int f = 0; f < _F.length; f++)
            {
                int goals = _F[f].getGoals().length;
                _goalToSpecimenArrayIndex[f] = new
                    int[goals];
                for (int g = 0; g < goals; g++)
                    _goalToSpecimenArrayIndex[f][g] =
                        arrayID++;
            }
        }

        /**
         * Can be called to update normalizations
         * maintained by the goals. At also
         * requires reevaluating the scores
         * linked
         * to their assigned solutions.
         *
         * @param normalizations new
         * normalizations used to rescale

```

```

    objective function values
*/
public void updateNormalizations(
    INormalization[] normalizations)
{
    for (Family F : _F)
        for (IGoal G : F.getGoals())
            G.updateNormalizations(
                normalizations);
}

/**
 * Getter for the families of goals.
 *
 * @return families of goals
 */
public Family[] getFamilies()
{
    return _F;
}
}

```

It is, however, often recommended to extend this point slightly above these limits, e.g., to 1.1 coordinates, so that the extreme Pareto points may still contribute to the overall HV.

Further, there is a “*presorting*” flag. If true, the procedure will start by monotonically presorting the input data points on the first objective. It is recommended to keep it true, as it can reduce the overall computational time (as explained in [8]). Then, the “*policyForNonDominated*” field determines how the analyzed normalized points that do not dominate the reference point should contribute to hypervolume (such points do not belong to the space spanned from the utopia to the reference point). See the inner “*PolicyForNonDominated*” enum for the descriptions of available policies. Next, the “*deriveNonDominatedSet*” field can be set to true (default value) to indicate that the non-dominated specimens (only these can contribute to the hypervolume) should be derived by the calculation procedure itself (before calculating hypervolume). Finally, “*deriveUniqueSpecimens*” plays a similar role to “*deriveNonDominatedSet*” but concerns removing duplicated specimens (duplicated performance vectors; removal is done before deriving non-dominated specimens).

2.5. Performance indicators

This section briefly overviews the three performance indicators implemented in JECDM (see the *indicator.emo* package): Hypervolume (*HV* class), Generational Distance (*GD* class), and Inverted Generational Distance (*IGD* class). These are probably the most commonly used indicators in evolutionary multi-objective optimization. All of them implement the already introduced *IPerformanceIndicator* interface (maps *ea.EA* into double) and extend the general *AbstractPerformanceIndicator* class that assumes that the assessment should be based on the current population (*SpecimenContainer.getPopulation()*). The following section briefly discusses how to use these implementations.

2.5.1. Hypervolume

This section discusses how to suitably parameterize the *HV* object instance. Listing 27 presents the source code, focusing only on the parameterization-related fields (the parameterization is done via the params container). Note that this implementation is based on the WFG method for calculating hypervolumes [8]. Further, it is assumed that the hypervolume calculation is done in the normalized space. That is, the relevant part of the objective space (e.g., the one that is spanned on the Pareto front) must be transformed into the standardized $[0, 1]^M$ hypercube.

First, the “*M*” integer denotes the number of objectives. Next, the normalization objects can be provided to execute the rescaling of the original objective space. For instance, for the WFG test problems, these can be linear normalizations with the min and max values set to 0 and $2m$ (where m is the objective number, starting from 1) because these are the true bounds for the Pareto front in these problems. Then, the “*rp*” is the reference point treated as the upper bound for hypervolume calculations. Note that the coordinates must be provided in the already normalized space. Thus, if $rp = \bar{1}$, the reference point matches the upper limits imposed by the normalization objects.

Listing 27: HV class

```

/**
 * A WFG implementation for the hypervolume
 * calculation (see <a href="https://
 * ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?
 * arnumber=5766730">...</a>).
 * Note that this implementation bounds the
 * space using a normalized hypercube  $[0,
 * 1]^{\text{the number of objectives } M}$ .
 * The scaling (i.e., mapping specimens
 * into a hypercube) is controlled by
 * provided normalization objects
 * ({@link INormalization}, each for a
 * different objective. It is assumed that
 * all the objectives
 * are to be minimized, and the 0-vector
 * represents the best attainable
 * objective vector. In turn, the R-vector
 * is the
 * upper bound, i.e., the reference point
 * used for hypervolume calculation.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class HV extends
    AbstractPerformanceIndicator implements
    IPerformanceIndicator
{
    [...]

    /**
     * The number of objectives.
     */
    private final int _M;

    /**
     * Normalizations used to map specimens

```

```

    into  $[0-1]^{\{the\ number\ of\ objectives\ M\}}$  hypercube. There should be
    * exactly M such objects provided, each
      linked to a different objective. Note
      that the normalizations
    * can be null (not used) -> the
      evaluation vectors are explicitly
      used when calculating the hypervolume
    .
  */
private final INormalization[]
    _normalizations;

/**
 * Reference point. Provides the upper
   bound for the objective space.
 * The reference point is assumed to be
   already normalized.
 */
private final double[] _rp;

/**
 * If true, the data points are pre-
   sorted monotonically on the first
   objective, before calculating HV.
 * It speeds up the calculations.
 */
private final boolean _presorting;

/**
 * Policies for contribution assessment
   for normalized points that do not
   dominate the reference point.
 */
private final PolicyForNonDominated
    _dominatedPolicy;

/**
 * If true, the method first derives the
   non-dominated set from the input
   specimens set (or from the already
   derived
 * unique vectors; for efficiency, it is
   recommended to use this mode).
 */
public boolean _deriveNonDominatedSet;

/**
 * If true, the method first derives
   unique specimens (in terms of their
   performance vectors) from the input
 * specimens set (it is recommended to
   use this mode; note that the unique
   specimens are derived before deriving
 * non-dominated ones).
 */
public boolean _deriveUniqueSpecimens;

[... ]
}

```

2.5.2. Example uses #3

Source package:
t1_t10.t3_evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.
t3_performanceindicators.t1_hv

This example tutorial showcases how the *HV* class can be used in practice. The source code for this case is in Listing 28.

Consider the following scenario:

- The number of objectives is 2.
- The relevant part of the objective space is in $[1, 2]$ and $[0, 4]$ intervals according to the first and second objective, respectively.
- The first objective is to be maximized, while the second is to be minimized.

The first lines of code in Listing 28 create the objective space object having the above properties. Next, the standard normalization builder object is constructed to create the suitable normalization objects, i.e., $1 - (value - 1) / (2 - 1)$ for the first objective, and $(value - 0) / (4 - 0)$ for the second. Therefore, the point with $[2, 0]$ coordinates will be normalized into $[0, 0]$ point (assume to be the best one). In turn, $[1, 4]$ will be mapped into $[1, 1]$.

The following lines instantiate the data set prepared for this case (4 points): $[1.5, 2.0]$, $[1.0, 0.0]$, $[2.0, 4.0]$, $[1.0, 4.0]$. Note that one extra point is specified $(2.0, 0.0)$, but is commented out). This is a utopia point, and employing it in the calculations should result in a hypervolume equal to 1.0 (100%). Additionally, one point is redundant as it is a dominated point (the last one).

Next a reference point – upper bound – is introduced. The point must be specified in the normalized space. Hence, a point $[1, 1]$ can be considered a utopia.

In what follows, the *HV* indicator object is constructed. The used parameterization is as follows (the order matches the order in which the parameters are provided):

- 2: 2-dimensional space is considered;
- *normalization*: normalization objects;
- *rp*: the upper bound for the normalized space;

The code instantiates next a dummy instance of the evolutionary algorithm (*EADummyPopulations* class; the indicator object performs the evaluation based on the input evolutionary algorithm). It allows for providing fixed (expected) performance matrices that will be used to construct dummy populations. The matrices will be returned cyclically in subsequent steps of the algorithm (“*init()*” and “*step()*” methods). If one matrix is supplied, then this dummy implementation will always return the same – fixed – population, which is desired in this synthetical experiment. The matrix passed as input is the data *double* $[[[]]]$ matrix instantiated before.

Finally, the “*init()*” method of the dummy algorithm is called to prepare the dummy population, followed by calling the

`hv.evaluate()` method to evaluate this population given the hypervolume indicator. The expected outcome is 0.25.

Listing 28: Calculation of HV – use case

```

Criteria criteria = Criteria.
    constructCriteria(new String[]{"C1", "C2"},
        new boolean[]{true, false});

// Bound for the first objective (to be
// maximized): [1, 2].
Range b1 = new Range(1.0d, 2.0d);
boolean d1 = true;

// Bound for the second objective (to be
// minimized): [0, 4].
Range b2 = new Range(0.0d, 4.0d);
boolean d2 = false;

// Objective space
ObjectiveSpace OS = new ObjectiveSpace(new
    Range[]{b1, b2}, new boolean[]{d1, d2});
// Construct normalization builder:
INormalizationBuilder nb = new
    StandardLinearBuilder();
// Construct normalizations:
INormalization[] normalizations = nb.
    getNormalizations(OS);

// Print normalization data:
for (INormalization n : normalizations)
    System.out.println(n.toString());

// Create the data (in the original space)
double[][] data = new double[][]
{
    //{2.0d, 0.0d}, utopia, adding this point
    // will set the HV to 100%
    {1.5d, 2.0d},
    {1.0d, 0.0d},
    {2.0d, 4.0d},
    {1.0d, 4.0d}, // dominated point
};

// Reference point used for HV calculation
// (nadir + normalized).
double[] rp = new double[]{1.0d, 1.0d};
//double [] rp = new double[] {1.1d, 1.1d};
// the RP can be extended to ensure
// that the extreme points will contribute
// to HV

// Create the HV instance:
HV hv = new HV(new HV.Params(2,
    normalizations, rp, new Dominance(
    criteria)));

// The indicator accepts an EA for the
// input (not double[][]). Hence, we can
// create a "dummy"
// EA that wraps predefined populations (
// expressed as double[][][]).

```

```

EADummyPopulations eaDummyPopulations = new
    EADummyPopulations(2, new double[][][] {
    data});

// The init method is called to set the
// initial population:
try
{
    eaDummyPopulations.init();
} catch (EAException e)
{
    throw new RuntimeException(e);
}

// Calculate HV and print it:
System.out.println("HV = " + hv.evaluate(
    eaDummyPopulations));

```

Figure 8 provides an illustrative representation of the above scenario. Its left side depicts the original solution space (i.e., before normalization). Noticeably, there are three non-dominated points, and one dominated ($[1, 4]$). The right side is the normalized counterpart. Note that the preference direction for the X-axis changed due to the standardization in normalization ($\mathbf{0}$ -vector is the utopia point). Noticeably, the dominated point (the coordinates are $[1, 1]$ after the normalization) does not contribute to hypervolume. Moreover, the extreme points (i.e., $[0, 1]$ and $[1, 0]$) do not contribute as well. This is due to how the upper bound (reference point) was specified. Its coordinates, i.e., $[1, 1]$, zero the surface of the area that contains points dominated by these extreme points. Consequently, only the middle point ($[0.5, 0.5]$) contributes to the final hypervolume, which equals $0.5^2 = 0.25$.

Figure 8: Hypervolume when the reference point is set to $[1, 1]$

The diminishing role of extreme solutions when calculating the hypervolume is a well-known issue. A common resolution to this problem is to shift the upper bounds slightly beyond the nadir point. As an example, Figure 9 illustrates what would happen if the reference point was set to $[1.1, 1.1]$ (instead of $[1, 1]$) (in this implementation of HV, the reference point can be set independently to normalization objects that are implicitly defining utopia and nadir points). This minor change made the extreme points relevant for calculations (although they still contribute less than the middle point). This time, the hypervolume equals $0.6^2 + 2(0.1 \cdot 0.5) = 0.46$.

Figure 9: Hypervolume when the reference point is set to [1.1, 1.1]

2.5.3. Generational distance and Inverted Generational Distance

The Generational Distance (GD) and Inverted Generational Distance (IGD) are well-known performance indicators. They are implemented in the *GD* and *IGD* classes in *indicator.emo* package.

Assume that P is the population, s a population member's objective vector, RP set of provided reference points (objective vectors; typically assumed to be Pareto optimal vectors that are uniformly distributed throughout the Pareto front), rp is a reference objective vector stored in rp , and $dist()$ is a function that quantifies a distance between two objective vectors.

The GD indicator measures the average distance from a population member to its nearest reference point, which can be expressed as follows:

$$GD(P, RP, dist) = \frac{1}{|P|} \sum_{s \in P} (\min \{dist(s, rp) : rp \in RP\}). \quad (1)$$

In turn, IGD takes an opposite perspective and measures the average distance from a reference point to its nearest population member:

$$IGD(P, RP, dist) = \frac{1}{|RP|} \sum_{rp \in RP} (\min \{dist(s, rp) : s \in P\}). \quad (2)$$

While GD accounts only for convergence, IGD may also assess the attained distribution of solutions. Both indicators are intuitive and easy to comprehend. Nonetheless, they have a drawback that may exclude their use in specific contexts. Specifically, they require a reference set to be provided. This implies that the Pareto front must be known in advance, and its Pareto optimal points must be easy to calculate. These conditions are easy to satisfy when dealing with a synthetical problem with a straightforward shape of the Pareto front (e.g., spherical), but it may be really challenging to use these indicators when solving a real-world optimization problem. Moreover, the final results are highly sensitive to the distribution of the reference points. Hence, one needs to be careful when using such performance measures. Naturally, one can use them more creatively, which may not require having Pareto optimal solutions. For instance, one could use them to directly compare two methods (one population becomes the reference set, while the other is the assessed population, and vice-versa).

2.5.4. Example uses #4

Source package:
t1_t10.t3_evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.
t3_performanceindicators.t2_rpsgenerator

The initial release of JECMD provides a basic means for generating Pareto optimal points for DTLZ and WFG problems. This section showcases how to generate them (using *GD* and *IGD* classes is relatively easy, so it is skipped in the following example uses).

Consider first the **Tutorial2a** source code. It presents how to employ the *ReferencePointsFactory* (*problem.moo* package) class to generate a desired number of reference points for a selected problem. Listing 29 brings the most relevant code snippet focused on creating the reference set. The code is self-explanatory and, thus, does not need to be discussed.

Listing 29: Generating random Pareto optimal points

```
// random number generator
IRandom R = new MersenneTwister64(0);
// the number of objectives (should be >=
2)
int M = 2;
// the number of random samples to
construct
int n = 1000;

// Set the problem ID
Problem problem = Problem.DTLZ1;

// Create reference points
double [][] rps = ReferencePointsFactory.
    getRandomReferencePoints(problem, n, M,
R);
```

Figure 10 illustrates three example reference sets of size 10, 100, and 1000, generated for the two-dimensional DTLZ1 test problem (plotted by the source code using the *Visualization* module).

Using randomly generated reference points may not be the best idea when assessing populations generated by an evolutionary algorithm as it may introduce some bias into measurements. These points should rather be distributed uniformly (nonetheless, “uniformness” is an ill-defined concept in this context). To aid in creating such a set, the *ReferencePointsFactory* delivers a “*getFilteredReferencePoints*” method. It first creates a desired number of random points. Then, it uses the provided optimization goals (implementations of the already introduced *IGoal* interface) to perform additional filtering. Specifically, the method identifies the best performer for each provided goal and returns all points found in this way as a filtered reference set.

The **Tutorial2b** source code showcases how to create the filtered reference set. The most relevant code snippet is provided in Listing 30. First, the code employs the *GoalsFactory* class to create a set of L_α^w -norm with weights (weighted Chebyshev functions) generated using the Das and Dennis’ method. The

Figure 10: Random Pareto optimal points generated for the DTLZ1 problem with two objectives.

constructed in this way optimization goals are passed to the “*getFilteredReferencePoints*” of *ReferencePointsFactory* class to identify Pareto optimal points being the closest to the provided L_α^n -norms. Figure 11a illustrates the obtained set for the 2D DTLZ1 problem. Additionally, Figure 11b showcases which points would be returned if $\alpha = 2$ had been used when generating L_α^n -norms (weighted Euclidean functions).

Listing 30: Generating filtered Pareto optimal points

```

// Construct reference goals (29 = the
// number of cuts for the Das and Dennis'
// method):
IGoal [] goals = GoalsFactory.getLNormsDND(
    M, 29, Double.POSITIVE_INFINITY, bundle.
    _normalizations);
//IGoal [] goals = GoalsFactory.
//getLNormsDND(M, 29, 2.0d, bundle.
//_normalizations);

// Create n random points but return a
// subset of them; identify the best
// performer among the random ones for each
// goal; return all of these best
// performers found.
double [][] rps = ReferencePointsFactory.
    getFilteredReferencePoints(problem, n, M
    , R, goals);

```

Important notes: It is not guaranteed that the filtered set will include the actual Pareto optimal best performers to the provided goals. The reason is that the filtering is done on the randomly created set of points. The more points requested to be generated at this step, the better the final relevance of the filtered points will be. Furthermore, the filtering may take some time for more extensive scenarios (e.g., when many random points are generated randomly, and many goals are provided as the input). Consequently, it is recommended to preconstruct and store such sets on a disc in practical applications (and load them just once during experimentation). The initial release of JECMD does not provide such preconstructed sets, as the number of possible configurations leading to different outcomes is

massive. Thus, it is better to let the users generate the reference sets in a way that best suits their needs.

Finally, the **Tutorial2c** source code was used to illustrate example filtered sets for all DTLZ and WFG problems with 2, 3, and 4 objective functions considered. The optimization goals employed were the functions that calculate the orthogonal distance from a point to a reference line. Figures 12-17 illustrate the obtained results.

Figure 11: Random Pareto optimal points generated for the DTLZ1 problem with two objectives, filtered using 30 L_α^n whose weights were generated using Das and Dennis’ method.

Figure 12: Random Pareto optimal points generated for DTLZ1-7 problems with 2 objectives, filtered using 30 functions quantifying the point's orthogonal distance to the line whose direction reference points were generated using Das and Dennis' method.

Figure 13: Random Pareto optimal points generated for DTLZ1-7 problems with 3 objectives, filtered using 91 functions quantifying the point's orthogonal distance to the line whose direction reference points were generated using Das and Dennis' method.

Figure 14: Random Pareto optimal points generated for DTLZ1-7 problems with 4 objectives, filtered using 165 functions quantifying the point's orthogonal distance to the line whose direction reference points were generated using Das and Dennis' method.

Figure 15: Random Pareto optimal points generated for WFG1-9 problems with 2 objectives, filtered using 30 functions quantifying the point's orthogonal distance to the line whose direction reference points were generated using Das and Dennis' method.

Figure 16: Random Pareto optimal points generated for WFG1-9 problems with 3 objectives, filtered using 91 functions quantifying the point's orthogonal distance to the line whose direction reference points were generated using Das and Dennis' method.

Figure 17: Random Pareto optimal points generated for WFG1-9 problems with 4 objectives, filtered using 165 functions quantifying the point's orthogonal distance to the line whose direction reference points were generated using Das and Dennis' method.

3. Implemented methods

This section discusses the four evolutionary methods for multi-objective optimization implemented for the initial release of the framework: NSGA [9], NSGA-II [1], NSGA-III [5], and MOEA/D [4]. Note that the following will primarily focus on showcasing how these methods were developed from the top-level perspective (e.g., establishing the processing flow) instead of thoroughly revising the lower-level components (e.g., class assisting in the crowding distance calculations). The latter is left to the reader for the examination. Overall, the primary motivation for this section is to provide the reader an insight into the development process (not the algorithms per se) so that (s)he may start implementing their own algorithms.

3.1. NSGA

NSGA [9] follows the same evolutionary scheme thoroughly examined in the previous tutorial document “Tutorial 2: Evolutionary Computation module – part 1: Basics and single-objective optimization” (generational updates, population-based, two parents per offspring, etc). Therefore, its implementation in JECDM widely uses the default phase components and adjusts just a few points in the processing flow to perform as expected.

Figure 18 illustrates the default algorithmic flow already introduced in the previous tutorial document. However, adaptations made to implement the NSGA algorithm are additionally marked on the presented scheme for convenience. Noticeably, just a few modifications are applied to the original model.

First, the sorting phase was implemented to act as imposed by NSGA (in fact, NSGA is the **sorting** algorithm; hence, in some sense, NSGA is just this one phase). Next, a dedicated *IOSChangeListener* was implemented and provided to the *ObjectiveSpaceManager* handled by the “Update objective space” phase. Anytime a change is reported, the listener constructs new normalization objects and passes them to the sorting phase. The implemented NSGA phase uses normalization objects when calculating niche counts. Finally, the model resigns from explicitly using the “Remove” phase. The removal of the excess of the population (the worst half) is executed by the sorting phase itself, as it was more convenient from the computational perspective when developing the algorithm.

All the codes that, when combined, form the NSGA method can be found in the *emo.aposteriori.nsga* package. Note that the *NSGA* class provides means for constructing the instance of the method represented as the top-level *EA* class.

Listing 31 brings the *NSGABundle* class for convenience. Noticeably, it is a relatively short source code. Note that the bundle extends the *AbstractEMOBundle* (*emo* package) class that nulls, by default, the “sort” and “remove” phases. Following the framework’s conventions, the implemented bundle has a dedicated inner *Params* class that introduces two parameterization fields related to calculating niche counts: “*_distance*” and “*_th*”. The former is a distance function employed to quantify the proximity of points (see the *space.normalization* package in the *Utils* module), while the latter is the proximity threshold

(the distance function can be supplied with the normalization objects to perform suitable rescaling).

Next, *NSGABundle* introduces a field dedicated to the implemented sorting phase: *NSGASort*. This phase is instantiated later in the “*instantiateSortPhase*” method (called by the constructor of the superclass – *AbstractEABundle*). In what follows, the “*getOSChangeListeners*” method is overwritten to create and return a dedicated *NSGAOSChangeListener* object. Note that this method is called by the “*registerOSChangeListeners*” method that is also implemented in the superclass and called in its constructor. Finally, the “*registerInitialNormalizations*” method is overwritten to conditionally supply the sorting phase with the initial normalization objects provided via the params container. This method is called in the constructor by *AbstractEABundle* after all the phases are created. Therefore, “*_nsgaSort*” should be instantiated at this step).

Listing 31: NSGABundle class

```
public class NSGABundle extends
    AbstractEMOBundle
{
    /**
     * Params container for the bundle getter
     */
    public static class Params extends
        AbstractEMOBundle.Params
    {
        /**
         * Distance function used when
         * calculating niche counts
         */
        public IDistance _distance = new
            Euclidean();

        /**
         * Distance threshold for the niche
         * count procedure
         */
        public double _th = 0.1d;

        /**
         * Parameterized constructor.
         *
         * @param criteria considered criteria
         */
        public Params(Criteria criteria)
        {
            super("NSGA", criteria);
        }
    }

    /**
     * Reference to the NSGA sorting phase
     */
    public NSGASort _nsgaSort = null;

    [...]
}
```


Figure 18: Basic scheme of the implemented NSGA algorithm

```

/**
 * Auxiliary method instantiating the
 * NSGA-dedicated "sort" phase.
 *
 * @param p params container
 */
@Override
protected void instantiateSortPhase(
    AbstractEABundle.Params p)
{
    Params pp = (Params) p;
    _nsgaSort = new NSGASort(p._criteria,
        pp._distance, pp._th);
    _phasesBundle._sort = _nsgaSort;
}

/**
 * Auxiliary method for retrieving NSGA-
 * dedicated OS changed listener
 * @param p params container
 * @return OS changed listeners.
 */
@Override
protected IOSChangeListener []
    getOSChangedListeners(AbstractEABundle
        .Params p)
{
    NSGAOSChangeListener l = new
        NSGAOSChangeListener(_nsgaSort, new
        StandardLinearBuilder());
    return new IOSChangeListener []{l};
}

/**
 * Provides initial normalization data to
 * selected objects.
 *
 * @param p params container
 */
@Override
protected void
    registerInitialNormalizations(
        AbstractEABundle.Params p)
{
    if (p._initialNormalizations != null)
        _nsgaSort.updateNormalizations(p.
            _initialNormalizations);
}
}

```

Listing 32 showcases the dedicated *NSGAOSChangeListener* class (its main “*action*” method only). The implemented procedure is straightforward. It first creates the normalization objects using the employed normalization builder object (handled by the superclass) and the data on the current objective space. Then, it passes these constructed objects to the sorting phase by calling the “*updateNormalizations*” method.

Listing 32: NSGAOSChangeListener class (action method)

```
/**
```

```

 * Updates normalizations.
 * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
 * @param os objective space (updated)
 * @param prevOS objective space (outdated;
 * for comparison)
 * @throws PhaseException the exception can
 * be thrown and propagated higher
 */
@Override
public void action(EA ea, ObjectiveSpace os
    , ObjectiveSpace prevOS) throws
    PhaseException
{
    _sort.updateNormalizations(_builder.
        getNormalizations(os));
}

```

Finally, Listing 33 brings the source code of the *NSGASort* class, which is the core part of the developed NSGA method. When it comes to its constructor, the passed distance function and the proximity threshold are used to instantiate two objects: *FNDSorting* (*emo.utils.front* package) and *NicheCount* (*emo.utils.density* package). The former is obviously responsible for executing the non-dominated sorting procedure (primary sorting criterion). At the same time, the latter provides a means for calculating the niche count values.

When it comes to the main method, i.e., “*action*”, it starts with creating a new specimen array (“*newPopulation*”) that will replace the current one after the sorting (therefore, no removal phase is needed). Then, the *FNDSorting* object is employed to partition the current population into non-dominated fronts (*FNDSorting.getFrontAssignments* method). Note that:

- The method, by default, terminates after at least “population size” of specimens is assigned to non-dominated fronts (the remaining specimens would be ignored anyway).
- The return type is: *LinkedList<LinkedList<Integer>>*. The external list captures all non-dominated fronts established, while the inner provides data on one front (the fronts are ordered from the best to the worst, i.e., the first element of the external list is the true (first) non-dominated front). The data stored in the inner list are indices of specimens stored in the current population (*SpecimenContainer.getPopulation()*) that have been assigned to the front. Hence, the method does not create an explicit split of the input array. Instead, it uses indices for the partitioning result, which is more convenient from the computational perspective.
- The method already sets auxiliary scores to specimens assigned to some non-dominated front. The score equals the non-dominated front number (integers starting from zero = the best front). These scores will be used later by the phase to sort solutions (and to determine which should not be passed to the next generation).

Next, the *FNDSorting.fillNewPopulationWithCertainFronts* method is invoked. It passes the current population members

into the “*newPopulation*” specimen array, as imposed by the non-dominated fronts. Note that the method can return an *AmbiguousFront* (inner class of *FNDSorting*). It will be returned only when some of the specimens that belong to the last front must be rejected due to exceeding the population size limit (otherwise the method returns null). The “ambiguous front” returns various data that may help resolve this situation (e.g., the number of already passed solutions, the population size limit, the ambiguous front number, etc.). Suppose there is such ambiguity in determining which solutions of the last front should be passed. In that case, the method applies the secondary sorting criterion that involves calculating the niche counts (the “*if (aFront != null)*” block).

The block starts with instantiating the “*lastFront*” specimen array that will be filled with a desired number of specimens (to reach – in total – the expected population size) that attain the best niche counts. Then, the “*_NC.getNicheCountInFront*” method is invoked to calculate the niche counts of all specimens that are in the last front (which cannot be completely passed due to the population capacity violation). After the calculations are done, the method sets the auxiliary values of the specimens in the last front to *last front number + specimen's niche count / max niche count* (the lower the niche count, the better; the smaller the auxiliary values, the better; the niche count is divided just for score normalization). This way, all the candidate specimens are considered slightly worse than those already passed to the new population. Further, these candidates can be ranked according to their niche counts. After assigning the auxiliary scores, the “*lastFront*” array is sorted according to its specimens’ auxiliary scores (in ascending order). Then, finally, the required number of first specimens in this array is passed to the new population, which overwrites the current population in the specimen container.

Listing 33: NSGASort class

```

/**
 * Implementation of NSGA sorting procedure
 * . Note that this phase overwrites the
 * current population. Hence, there is no
 * need to call the "remove" phase.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class NSGASort extends
    AbstractSortPhase implements IPhase
{
    /**
     * Parameterized constructor.
     *
     * @param criteria considered criteria
     * @param distance distance function used
     * when calculating niche counts
     * @param th distance threshold for the
     * niche count procedure
     */
    public NSGASort(Criteria criteria,
        IDistance distance, double th)
    {
        super("NSGA: Sort");
        _FND = new FNDSorting(new Dominance(
            criteria));
        _NC = new NicheCount(distance, th);
    }

    /**
     * Normalizations used when calculating
     * niche counts.
     */
    private INormalization[] _normalizations
        = null;

    /**
     * Object responsible for identifying non
     * -dominated fronts.
     */
    private final FNDSorting _FND;

    /**
     * Supportive object for calculating
     * niche counts.
     */
    private final NicheCount _NC;

    /**
     * Phase's main action.
     *
     * @param ea evolutionary algorithm
     * @param report report on the executed
     * action (to be filled)
     * @throws PhaseException the exception
     * can be thrown and propagated higher
     */
    @Override
    public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
        report) throws PhaseException
    {
        // Instantiate new population
        ArrayList<Specimen> newPopulation = new
            ArrayList<>(ea.getPopulationSize())
            ;

        // Identify the required number of non-
        dominated fronts
        LinkedList<LinkedList<Integer>> fronts
            = _FND.getFrontAssignments(
                new Specimens(ea.getSpecimensContainer
                    ().getPopulation()), ea,
                    getPopulationSize());

        // Pass as many fronts as possible and
        determine the ambiguous front
        // Note that the procedure sets
        specimens' aux scores: defined as
        the front level (starting from zero)

        FNDSorting.AmbiguousFront aFront =
            FNDSorting.
                fillNewPopulationWithCertainFronts(
                    newPopulation,
                    ea.getSpecimensContainer()).
    }

```

```

        getPopulation(), fronts, ea.
        getPopulationSize());

60 // only if there is an ambiguous front
    if (aFront != null)
    {
        // construct the ambiguous population
65 ArrayList<Specimen> lastFront = new
        ArrayList<>(ea.getPopulationSize()
            - aFront._passedMembers);

        // there is a need to calculate niche
        counts.
        double[] nc = _NC.
            getNicheCountInFront(aFront._front
            , ea.getSpecimensContainer().
            getPopulation(), _normalizations);
        double div = StatUtils.max(nc);

70
        int num = 0;
        for (Integer idx : aFront._front)
        {
            lastFront.add(ea.
                getSpecimensContainer().
                getPopulation().get(idx));
75 lastFront.get(num).setAuxScore(
            aFront._passedFronts + (nc[num]
            / div));
            num++;
        }

        sort.Sort.sortByAuxValue(lastFront,
            true);
80 for (int i = 0; i < ea.
            getPopulationSize() - aFront.
            _passedMembers; i++)
            newPopulation.add(lastFront.get(i));
    }

    // overwrite the population
85 ea.getSpecimensContainer().
        setPopulation(newPopulation);
}

[...]
```

3.1.1. Example use [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t3_evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.
t4_algorithms.t1_nsga

This tutorial explains how to employ the implemented NSGA algorithm in practice. Notably, the methods implemented in JECDM require extensive parameterization due to the focus on code generalization. To alleviate this problem, a dedicated NSGA class is introduced to hide as much parameterization as possible. It is an extension of the EA class and is available in

emo.aposteriori.nsga package. The reader is encouraged to inspect its code.

Nonetheless, nothing really new is introduced in this tutorial. Therefore, the code snippets are not presented here to keep the document concise. It is up to the reader to study them. Overall, the tutorial introduces the following scenario:

- NSGA is applied to DTLZ2 and WFG problems with $M = 2, 3,$ and 4 objectives. Regarding the latter, a less challenging bias level of $\alpha = 0.5$ was used. The original value of 0.02 gives an optimization problem that is practically unsolvable when a standard double format is employed (the mantissa is too short). Some studies acknowledge this issue and also consider a reduced bias (e.g., [10]). The value of $\alpha = 0.5$ makes the resulting WFG1 problem very easy to solve, but tackling challenging problems is not of concern in this section.
- The number of distance-related parameters for DTZ2 is set to $M + 5 - 1$ [2]. Regarding WFG1, the number of position and distance-related variables is $2(M - 1)$ and 20 [3].
- The thresholds for the distance in the niching procedure are 0 (effectively, it disables niche counts), 0.1 , and 2.0 . Note that the thresholds are utilized in the normalized space.
- The performances of these three instances of NSGA (parameterized with different thresholds) were measured using the HV indicator with a reference point set to $[1.1]^M$. Generated objective vectors that did not dominate the reference point were ignored when calculating the HV.
- The results are presented in a visualization window that consists of $3 \text{ rows} \times 2 \text{ columns} = 6$ plots. Each row is dedicated to one method. Its left plot is a scatter plot (for $M = 2$ and $M = 3$, for $M = 4$, a parallel coordinate plot was used) depicting all generations constructed throughout the optimization process (each population is rendered using a different color from a gradient). The right plot is a convergence plot illustrating attained HV across generations.
- The limit for the number of generations is set to 400 .
- The population sizes are set to 50 for $M = 2$, 100 for $M = 3$, and 200 for $M = 4$.
- Note that this example just exhibits how to use the implementation of NSGA in practice. It does not intend to run a methodologically complete analysis. Thus, the experiments are somewhat simplified (they do not even involve averaging the results across multiple independent executions of the method). But, again, this section – and the following ones – shows how to use the implementation, not how to perform a methodologically correct analysis. The latter will be in the scope of the tutorial document named: “Tutorial 5: Experimentation module”.

The expected results for DTLZ2 case are presented in Figure 19 ($M = 2$), 20 ($M = 3$), and 21 ($M = 4$), while for WFG are illustrated in Figure 22 ($M = 2$), 23 ($M = 3$), and 24 ($M = 4$). They are consistent with the well-known findings on NSGA. First, setting the threshold to a too-low value will effectively turn off the secondary sorting criterion (niche count). Hence, there will be no control over the population distribution. On the other hand, however, it may boost the convergence pace towards the Pareto front if there are just a few objectives, e.g., 2. In turn, if the threshold is too high, the optimizer will prefer extreme solutions, highly diminishing diversity and lowering the convergence pace as well. Consequently, a sweet spot must be found. In these three examples, the NSGA with the threshold of 0.1 can be considered the best performer when the distribution and the convergence are concerned simultaneously. Note that NSGA's performance is generally highly sensitive to the threshold value used, given the problem being solved. Small changes in other method parameters may also imply readjusting the threshold. For example, it should decrease with the increase in population size.

Figure 19: Results attained by NSGA applied to DTLZ2 with 2 objectives

Figure 20: Results attained by NSGA applied to DTLZ2 with 3 objectives

Figure 21: Results attained by NSGA applied to DTLZ2 with 4 objectives

Figure 22: Results attained by NSGA applied to WFG1 with 2 objectives

Figure 23: Results attained by NSGA applied to WFG1 with 3 objectives

Figure 24: Results attained by NSGA applied to WFG1 with 4 objectives

3.2. NSGA-II

The NSGA-II [1] method was implemented in JECDM in exactly the same spirit as NSGA. The sole difference is related to the fact that the former method employs a nonparametric crowding-distance measure to differentiate between non-dominated solutions that are candidates to be passed to the next generation. Therefore, codes are not brought here to avoid repetitions. Nonetheless, inspecting the codes available in the *emo.aposteriori.nsgaii* package is recommended. As with NSGA, a dedicated *NSGAIi* (extension of EA) class is introduced.

3.2.1. Example use [T]

```
Source package:  
t1_t10.t3_evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.  
t4_algorithms.t2_nsgaii
```

The tutorial showcased in this section is just a suitable adaptation of the one introduced in Section 3.1.1. Because NSGA-II does not involve any critical parameter, like the distance threshold for NSGA, only three scenarios were employed, each dedicated to different objective space dimensionality ($M = 2, 3, 4$). The results are provided in a single visualization window depicted in Figure 25 (DTLZ) and Figure 26 (WFG). They are consistent with the general knowledge on the NSGA-II performance.

In general, NSGA-II can approximate the two and three-dimensional Pareto fronts quite well. However, the overall performance is expected to start deteriorating (quite rapidly), beginning with four objectives. Note that the DTLZ2 has a concave Pareto front. In general, due to the characteristics of this problem, the generated objective vectors will tend to form concave structures. The crowding-distance measure does not handle concavity well; it favors vectors more distant to the Pareto front than the closest ones to maximize the crowding distances. In more dimensional spaces, the dominance relation rarely holds between pairs of solutions, leaving the secondary sorting criterion – crowding-distance metric – the only effective one. Consequently, in scenarios involving many objectives and concavities, the convergence to the Pareto front may not only be opposed but finally, the population may even be pushed back from the Pareto front.

Figure 25: Results attained by NSGA-II applied to DTLZ2

Figure 26: Results attained by NSGA-II applied to WFG1

3.3. NSGA-III

NSGA-III [5] follows the same design pattern as its two predecessors in JECDM (see the *emo.aposteriori.nsgaiii* package). The sole differences are related to the following:

- The method employs a *NSGAIIIGoalsManager* class that manages the decomposition-related processing (extends *AbstractGoalsManager*; see *emo.utils.decomposition.nsgaiii* package).
- The fundamental parameter used to tune the NSGA-III is a series of optimization goals provided via the goals manager (implementations of the *IGoal* interface).
- The listener for changes in the objective space creates and passes the normalization objects directly to the goals manager, as they are only used when making the assignments (specimens to goals).
- The primary sorting criterion is the same as in NSGA and NSGA-II. However, the code for the secondary sorting step employs the goals manager to perform the niching and the selection, determining which solutions from the ambiguous front should be passed to the next generation.

Note that, as with *NSGA* and *NSGAI*, a dedicated *NSGAI* (extension of *EA*) class is introduced.

The code snippets from the *NSGAIIBundle* class are brought in Listing 34 for convenience. Notably, there are three major fields with which the bundle must be supplied. First, the “*goalsManager*” is an instance of *NSGAIIGoalsManager*, which is responsible for performing the decomposition-related processing. Next, the “*_assignmentResolveTies*” and “*_specimenResolveTie*” are responsible for resolving potential ties that may occur when selecting a solution to be included in the population for the next generation (see [5] for details). Regarding the first, it is employed to resolve a tie when determining an assignment with a minimal niche count value. The second is responsible for returning an index of a specimen appointed to the selected assignment object (when there are many assignments and the assignment’s current niche count value is greater than 0). The default implementations in the initial release of JECDM are random selections. **Side note:** the current interfaces for these tie-resolving objects are oversimplified and may be extended in the future.

Listing 34: NSGAIIBundle.Params class

```

/**
 * Params container for the bundle.
 */
public static class Params extends
    AbstractEMOBundle.Params
{
    /**
     * Goals manager steering the
     * evolutionary process.
     */
    public final NSGAIIGoalsManager
        _goalsManager;

```

```

/**
 * Object used for resolving a tie when
 * selecting an assignment with a
 * minimal niche count
 */
public final IAssignmentResolveTie
    _assignmentResolveTie;

/**
 * Object used when resolving a tie
 * during a selection of a specimen when
 * the associated assignment object has
 * a niche count value greater than one
 */
public final ISpecimenResolveTie
    _specimenResolveTie;

/**
 * Parameterized constructor.
 *
 * @param criteria      considered criteria
 * @param goalsManager  NSGA-III goals
 *                       manager
 * @param assignmentResolveTie object
 *                       used for resolving a tie when
 *                       selecting an assignment with a
 *                       minimal niche count
 * @param specimenResolveTie object
 *                       responsible for resolving a tie when
 *                       selecting from multiple solutions
 *                       assigned to a goal with niche count >
 *                       1
 */
public Params(Criteria criteria,
              NSGAIIGoalsManager goalsManager,
              IAssignmentResolveTie
                assignmentResolveTie,
              ISpecimenResolveTie specimenResolveTie
            )
{
    super("NSGA-III", criteria);
    _goalsManager = goalsManager;
    _assignmentResolveTie =
        assignmentResolveTie;
    _specimenResolveTie =
        specimenResolveTie;
}
}

```

Consider now the Listing 35 that provides code snippets from the *NSGAIIGoalsManager* class. It is up to the reader to get acquainted with the details of such lower-level implementations. Nonetheless, the showcased code is brought here to serve as a convenient tutorial example.

The “*executeAssignmentStep*” method is run first by NSGA-III when there is an ambiguity in deciding which specimen should be passed to the next generation. It calculates the initial niche count values and assigns candidate solutions to their most relevant optimization goals.

The method starts with clearing the assignment data (niche

counts, assigned specimens, and their evaluations). Then, it iterates over the constructed non-dominated fronts (the first fronts that “fit” with the population capacity and the last front that is called ambiguous). Within one front, the method iterates over its assigned specimens (derived using the array index). The loop starts by determining an optimization goal that is “the closest” to the specimen being processed. Next, the goal’s linked assigned object is derived. Finally, the assignment’s niche count value is increased by one if the front being processed is not the last one (its solutions are passed to the next generation; hence, they can be used to set initial niche count values). If, however, the ambiguous front is being processed, the processed specimen is added to the assignment object instead. For this purpose, the “insertSpecimen” method is used. It adds the specimen and its relevance to the goal (calculated by the method) to the specimen and evaluation lists. The insertion preserves the order of specimens, i.e., they are kept sorted from the most to the least relevant ones.

Listing 35: NSGAIIGoalsManager class

```

/**
 * Class providing various functionalities
 * for maintaining/processing goals/
 * assignments in a
 * decomposition-based algorithm founded on
 * the NSGA-III algorithm.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class NSGAIIGoalsManager extends
    AbstractGoalsManager
{
    [...]

    /**
     * Method for performing the assignment
     * step. It assigns each population
     * member that is in the already passed
     * fronts
     * or the ambiguous front to its closest
     * goal. Additionally, the method sets
     * the initial niche count based on the
     * solutions that will certainly be
     * passed to the next generation (not in
     * the ambiguous front).
     *
     * @param population current population
     * @param fronts      passed fronts + the
     *                    ambiguous front (or just the last
     *                    front; if the size = 1); stored
     *                    integers are indices of associated
     *                    solutions in the current population
     *                    array
     */
    public void executeAssignmentStep(
        ArrayList<Specimen> population,
        LinkedList<LinkedList<Integer>> fronts
    )

```

```

{
    // reset assignments
    for (Family f : _F)
    {
        f.resetAssignmentsNicheCounts();
        f.resetAssignmentsLists();
    }

    boolean notLastFront;
    ListIterator<LinkedList<Integer>>
        listIt = fronts.listIterator();
    LinkedList<Integer> front;

    // for each specimen
    while (listIt.hasNext())
    {
        front = listIt.next();
        notLastFront = listIt.hasNext();

        for (Integer id : front)
        {
            Specimen specimen = population.get(
                id);
            // find the best assignment
            GoalID gID = findClosestGoal(
                specimen);
            // get the assignment
            Assignment assignment = _F[gID.
                getFamilyArrayIndex()].
                getAssignment(gID.
                    getGoalArrayIndex());

            // if not in the last (ambiguous)
            // front, increase NC
            if (notLastFront) assignment.
                incrementNicheCount();
            // else add a specimen to the
            // assignment
            else assignment.insertSpecimen(
                specimen);
        }
    }
}
}

```

Listing 36 showcases the “action” method of the *NSGAIISort* phase. As with NSGA and NSGA-III, the method starts with identifying the non-dominated fronts. If there is an ambiguity in which specimens should be passed to the next generation, the method performs the decomposition-based sorting (see the *if (aFront != null)* block).

The block starts with performing the initial assignments. Then, the following loop aims to add a missing number of specimens (from the ambiguous front) to the next iteration (one iteration selects one specimen). The loop first determines the assignments with minimal niche count values (the called procedure skips the empty assignments). If there is a tie, the dedicated policy resolves the selection problem. If the niche count value equals zero, meaning that no solution associated with this goal has been passed to the next generation yet, the as-

signment's best performer is selected. Otherwise, a selection policy is applied to choose the winner. The designated solution is then removed from the assignment object (updating the specimen/evaluation sorted lists this way), assigned an auxiliary score (slightly worse than the scores assigned to specimens belonging to the better – directly preceding – non-dominated front), and added to the new population being constructed. Finally, the niche count value of the assignment object to which the designated specimen was appointed is increased by one.

Listing 36: NSGAIISort class (action method)

```

// Instantiate new population
ArrayList<Specimen> newPopulation = new
    ArrayList<>(ea.getPopulationSize());

// Identify the required number of non-
// dominated fronts
5 LinkedList<LinkedList<Integer>> fronts =
    _FND.getFrontAssignments(
new Specimens(ea.getSpecimensContainer().
    getPopulation()), ea.getPopulationSize()
    );

// Pass as many fronts as possible and
// determine the ambiguous front
FNDSorting.AmbiguousFront aFront =
    FNDSorting.
    fillNewPopulationWithCertainFronts(
        newPopulation, ea.getSpecimensContainer
        ().getPopulation(), fronts, ea.
        getPopulationSize());
10

// only if there is an ambiguous front
if (aFront != null)
{
    // Execute assignment step (assign each
    // solution to its closest goal)
15 // the procedure also calculates initial
    // niching (used the solutions that must
    // be passed to the next generation)
    _goalsManager.executeAssignmentStep(ea.
        getSpecimensContainer().getPopulation
        (), fronts);

    // repeat the required number of times
    for (int i = 0; i < ea.getPopulationSize
        () - aFront._passedMembers; i++)
20 {
        // find goal (assignment) with the
        // minimal niche count
        LinkedList<Assignment> assignments =
            _goalsManager.
            getAssignmentsWithMinimalNicheCount(
                true);
        Assignment assignment;
        if (assignments.size() > 1) assignment
            = _assignmentResolveTie.resolveTie(
                assignments, ea.getR());
25 else assignment = assignments.getFirst
            ();
    }
}

```

```

int NC = (int) (assignment.
    getNicheCount() + 0.5d); // to avoid
    numerical errors

int specimenIndex = 0; // the best
// note that empty assignments are
// already ignored

if (NC > 1) specimenIndex =
    _specimenResolveTie.getSpecimenIndex
    (assignment.getSpecimens(), ea.getR
    ());

// assign some solution using the
// policy
Specimen specimen = assignment.
    getSpecimenAndRemoveFromLists(
        specimenIndex);
specimen.setAuxScore(aFront.
    _passedFronts + 0.5d);
newPopulation.add(specimen);
assignment.incrementNicheCount();
}
}
// overwrite the population
ea.getSpecimensContainer().setPopulation(
    newPopulation);

```

3.3.1. Example use [T]

Source package:

t1_t10.t3_evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.
t4_algorithms.t3_nsgaiii

The experiment uses the same pattern as for NSGA and NSGA-II. However, the population size is now determined by the number of optimization goals that are generated using the Das and Dennis' method (hence, it cannot be arbitrary). Overall, the size is 50 for $M = 2$, 91 for $M = 3$, and 220 for $M = 4$. Further, three variants of the NSGA-III method are examined. The first one involves the originally used orthogonal distance function to quantify the solution's relevance to an optimization goal. The JECDM, however, is founded on higher-level abstractions, and the developed algorithm can be supplied with goals that can take any reasonable form (scalarizing function). As for extra examinations, the Chebyshev functions and the penalty-based boundary intersection functions were used (the aggregating coefficient of 5 was utilized). Figures 27, 28, and 29 concern the results for DTLZ2, while Figures 30, 31, and 32 illustrate their counterparts for WFG1. The results clearly exhibit the superiority of NSGA-III over its predecessors.

Figure 27: Results attained by NSGA-III applied to DTLZ2 (orthogonal distances)

Figure 28: Results attained by NSGA-III applied to DTLZ2 (Chebyshev functions)

Figure 29: Results attained by NSGA-III applied to DTLZ2 (penalty-based boundary intersection functions with the aggregating coefficient of 5.0))

Figure 30: Results attained by NSGA-III applied to WFG1 (orthogonal distances)

Figure 31: Results attained by NSGA-III applied to WFG1 (Chebyshev functions)

Figure 32: Results attained by NSGA-III applied to WFG1 (penalty-based boundary intersection functions with the aggregating coefficient of 5.0)

3.4. MOEA/D

The MOEA/D [4] algorithm implemented in JECDM follows a different processing flow than the NSGA methods. It is mainly because MOEA/D is – by default – a steady-state method, which generates one offspring in one generation. It is reflected in JECDM by suitably adjusting the concept of an iteration. Specifically:

- It is considered that one generation consists of a series of steady-state repeats.
- One steady-step repeat is one iteration (thus, it is triggered by calling an evolutionary algorithm’s “step” method).
- The consistency of the generation and steady-state numbers (EATimestamp) is controlled by the *Runner* object.
- In one iteration (stead-state repeat), the method constructs one restricted mating pool, one *Parents* object (from the mating pool), and, finally, constructs one offspring (from the *Parents*) that may surpass current population members.
- It is assumed that the number of steady-state repeats equals the population size, which ultimately equals the number of optimization goals employed by MOEA/D.
- By default, one goal will be updated once in a single generation (each goal will be updated during a series of steady-state repeats). The update refers to constructing an offspring using the parents selected from the neighborhood of a currently processed goal (and, potentially, using it as a better replacement for specimens belonging to the neighborhood).

Additionally, a dedicated *MOEAD* (extension of EA) class is introduced for this algorithm.

Before discussing the general algorithmic flow, let us focus on the *MOEADGoalsManager* (see the *emo.utils.decomposition.moead* package; extends the *AbstractGoalsManager* class), a goals manager implementation that is dedicated to MOEA/D. Listing 37 brings its most relevant code snippets, but it is up to the reader to study this class.

Consider first the params container. In addition to the standard parameters (e.g., the optimization goals), the class extension introduces three additional parameterization means essential to MOEA/D. As the name suggests, the “*_neighborhoodSize*” field specifies the size of the neighborhood (the number of nearest goals – to a goal – that are considered neighbors; the goal is in its neighborhood). Next, object(s) implementing the *ISimilarity* interface can be specified (one object for one family of goals; see the *emo.utils.decomposition.similarity* package). The implementations of the *ISimilarity* interfaces are responsible for calculating the similarity (proximity) between two input goals. They are employed when establishing the neighborhoods (one neighborhood per one goal). Finally, the object implementing the *IAlloc* interface (see *emo.utils.decomposition.alloc* package) is responsible for determining the sequence of goals updates. Its

primary method (“getAllocations”) is called by MOEA/D at the beginning of each generation to determine which goals, in what order, and how many times should be updated in one generation. The return type of its method is an array of *GoalID* objects, where the *i*-th element is supposed to point to a goal to be updated during *i*-th steady state repeat. The default implementation in JECDM is the *Uniform* class that generates a random permutation – drawn from a uniform distribution of goals’ identifiers. This helps avoid a bias in search that could be imposed by executing the orders in an arbitrary and prefixed order.

Although it is up to the reader to study the *MOEADGoalsManager* class, some brief methods are brought in Listing 37 for convenience. For instance, the “*determineUpdateSequence*” can be called to generate the array of goals’ identifiers that determine the update sequence (the result is stored in the class field). Next, the “*getCurrentGoalToBeUpdated*” returns a goal (its ID) that is supposed to be updated in a given steady-state repeat. Further, “*getCurrentNeighborhood*” returns IDs of those goals belonging to a given input goal (ID) neighborhood. Finally, the “*establishNeighborhood*” method can be called to create *Neighborhood* object and instantiates its internal data. This method is called in the default implementation of MOEA/D during the initialization.

Listing 37: MOEADGoalsManager class

```
/**
 * Class providing various functionalities
 * for maintaining/processing goals/
 * assignments in a
 * decomposition-based algorithm founded on
 * the MOEA/D algorithm.
 *
 * @author MTomczyk
 */
public class MOEADGoalsManager extends
    AbstractGoalsManager
{
    /**
     * Params container.
     */
    public static class Params extends
        AbstractGoalsManager.Params
    {
        /**
         * Neighborhood size (should be at
         * least 1).
         */
        public int _neighborhoodSize;

        /**
         * Similarity measures used to compare
         * the goals within families (1:1 link
         * , i.e., no. elements should equal
         * no. row in the goals matrix).
         */
        public ISimilarity[] _similarity;

        /**
         * Used to allocate resources (
         * determines updates of goals in
```

```

        subsequent steady-state repeats
        within one generation).
    */
    public IAlloc _alloc = null;

    [...]

    /**
    * Parameterized constructor.
    * Establishes one-family decomposition
    * data. Insertion sort constructor {
    * @link InsertionSortConstructor}
    * is used when building neighborhoods.
    *
    * @param goals optimization
    * goals (the only family)
    * @param similarity similarity
    * measure used to compare the goals
    * @param neighborhoodSize neighborhood
    * size
    */
    public Params(IGoal[] goals,
        ISimilarity similarity, int
        neighborhoodSize)
    {
        this(new IGoal[][]{goals}, new
            ISimilarity[]{similarity}, new
            InsertionSortConstructor(),
            neighborhoodSize);
    }

    [...]
}

[...]

/**
* Sequence of goals updates obtained via
* {@link IAlloc} object.
*/
private GoalID[] _updatesSequence = null;

/**
* Parameterized constructor.
*
* @param p params container
*/
public MOEADGoalsManager(Params p)
{
    super(p);
    _S = p._similarity;
    _NC = p._neighborhoodConstructor;
    _neighborhoodSize = p._neighborhoodSize
        ;
    _alloc = p._alloc;
}

/**
* Can be called to construct a sequence
* of goal updates to be executed in

```

```

        subsequence steady-state repeats.
    *
    * @param R random number generator
    */
    public void determineUpdatesSequence(
        IRandom R)
    {
        _updatesSequence = _alloc.
            getAllocations(_F, R);
    }

    /**
    * Returns the current goal to be updated
    *
    * @param steadyStateRepeat steady-state
    * repeat no.
    * @return goal to be updated
    */
    public GoalID getCurrentGoalToBeUpdated(
        int steadyStateRepeat)
    {
        return _updatesSequence[
            steadyStateRepeat];
    }

    /**
    * Returns the current neighborhood of a
    * goal being updated.
    *
    * @param currentGoal points to the
    * current goal being updated
    * @return IDs of goals belonging to the
    * current neighborhood
    */
    public GoalID[] getCurrentNeighborhood(
        GoalID currentGoal)
    {
        return _N[currentGoal.
            getFamilyArrayIndex()].
            getNeighborhood(currentGoal.
            getGoalArrayIndex());
    }

    /**
    * Method for establishing neighborhoods.
    */
    public void establishNeighborhood()
    {
        _N = new Neighborhood[_F.length];
        for (int f = 0; f < _F.length; f++)
            _N[f] = _NC.getNeighborhood(_F[f], _S
                [f], _neighborhoodSize);
    }

    [...]
}

```

Figure 33 illustrates a general scheme imposed by the implemented method (see the *emo.aposteriori.moead* package and the *MOEADBundle* class). Unlike in the previous schemes, this

diagram omits all phases that are not employed by MOEA/D for brevity.

The method begins the initialization as usual: constructs the initial population, assigns specimen IDs, and performs the evaluation. However, there is no “*sort*” phase. MOEA/D implements an entirely different computational paradigm from the NSGA methods. Here, one offspring is generated per iteration, which may replace some population members if proven to perform better for their associated optimization goals. No global sorting is thus required. Regarding the “update objective space” phase, the dedicated listener passes updated normalization objects directly to *MOEADGoalsManager*, subsequently supplying the employed optimization goals with these new normalization functions. The initialization ends with calling a dedicated “init ends” phase. It performs three tasks (see Listing 38):

1. It first requests the *MOEADGoalManager* to establish the neighborhoods.
2. Then, the manager is asked to construct the goals update sequence.
3. Finally, the manager is requested to make initial (and arbitrary) assignments using the current population. The “arbitrary” means that the specimens will be assigned as they are, i.e., the *i*-th specimen will be assigned to the *i*-th goal. It is recommended to avoid greedy assignments at this step (i.e., find the best performers for each goal). As the original article points out, it could result in premature convergence caused by the diminished variability of specimens.

Listing 38: MOEADInitEnds class (action method)

```

@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
report) throws PhaseException
{
    _goalManager.establishNeighborhood();
    _goalManager.determineUpdatesSequence(ea.
getR());
    _goalManager.makeArbitraryAssignments(ea.
getSpecimensContainer());
}

```

As already explained, the implementation assumes that one generation will consist of multiple steady-state repeats, which equals the population size – thus, the number of employed goals. It is up to the employed runner to consistently iterate over generations and steady-state repeats (thus, to produce proper timestamps).

One step starts with executing an adjusted “prepare step” phase. It reconstructs the goals update sequence if the current steady-state repeat number equals 0, which means that it is the beginning of a generation. Then, the method proceeds to a dedicated “construct mating pool” phase. It creates a restricted mating pool consisting of specimens appointed to optimization goals in the neighborhood of a current goal being updated (see Listing 39).

Listing 39: MOEADConstructMatingPool class (action method)

```

@Override

```

```

public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
report) throws PhaseException
{
    GoalID GL = _goalManager.
getCurrentGoalToBeUpdated(ea.
getCurrentSteadyStateRepeat());
    ArrayList<Specimen> MP = _goalManager.
getMatingPool(GL);
    ea.getSpecimensContainer().setMatingPool(
MP);
}

```

After the mating pool is established, the algorithm creates one *Parents* object using the specimens in the restricted mating pool, creates one offspring, assigns its ID, and evaluates it. Regarding the selection, a random procedure is recommended as the mating pool is restricted and, thus, already consists of promising solutions. Next, the “update objective space” phase is executed. Finally, the last phase, i.e., the “finalize step” is called. The population update is done during this phase (see Listing 40). The “*action*” method first retrieves the goal being currently updated (ID) and the newly created offspring. Lastly, it requests the goals manager to execute an update given these two objects (see Listing 41). During the update, the offspring is compared against all specimens assigned to goals in the neighborhood. The offspring will replace the specimen in the goal assignment if it proves a better performer according to the goal. Note that the global examination, i.e., comparing the offspring with all population members is not recommended as it may cause premature convergence. Finally, the “*executeUpdate*” method will also conditionally – i.e., if the offspring yields an improvement – replace the population members (stored in the specimen container) with the offspring. The goals manager has a mapping *goal ID* → *index in the population array* that dictates which specimens should be replaced.

Listing 40: MOEADFinalizeStep class (action method)

```

@Override
public void action(EA ea, PhaseReport
report) throws PhaseException
{
    GoalID GL = _goalManager.
getCurrentGoalToBeUpdated(ea.
getCurrentSteadyStateRepeat());
    Specimen O = ea.getSpecimensContainer().
getOffspring().get(0);
    _goalManager.executeUpdate(O, GL, ea.
getSpecimensContainer());
}

```

Listing 41: MOADGoalsManager.executeUpdate(...) method

```

public void executeUpdate(Specimen
offspring, GoalID currentGoal,
SpecimensContainer specimensContainer)
{
    GoalID [] nb = getCurrentNeighborhood(
currentGoal);

    for (GoalID gl : nb)

```


Figure 33: Basic scheme of the implemented MOEA/D algorithm

```

{
    Family family = _F[gl.
        getFamilyArrayIndex()];
    IGoal goal = family.getGoal(gl.
        getGoalArrayIndex());
    double offspringEvaluation = goal.
        evaluate(offspring);
10

    Assignment currentAssignment = family.
        getAssignment(gl.getGoalArrayIndex()
        );
    if ((goal.isLessPreferred()) && (Double
        .compare(offspringEvaluation,
        currentAssignment.
        getFirstSpecimenEvaluation()) >= 0))
        continue;
    if ((!goal.isLessPreferred()) && (
        Double.compare(offspringEvaluation,
        currentAssignment.
        getFirstSpecimenEvaluation()) <= 0))
        continue;

15    // alter the assignment
    currentAssignment.
        setFirstSpecimenEvaluation(
        offspringEvaluation);
    currentAssignment.setFirstSpecimen(
        offspring);

    int populationID =
        _goalToSpecimenArrayIndex[gl.
        getFamilyArrayIndex()][gl.
        getGoalArrayIndex()];
20    specimensContainer.getPopulation().set(
        populationID, offspring);
}
}

```

3.4.1. Example use [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t3_evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.
t4_algorithms.t4_moead

The experimental setup in this section is the same as for NSGA-III. The neighborhood size for MOEA/D was set to 10, while the similarity between the goals was quantified as an Euclidean distance between their reference points (or weight vectors). Figures 34, 35, and 36 concern the results for DTLZ2, while Figures 37, 38, and 39 illustrate their counterparts for WFG1.

The results reveal the satisfactory performance of MOEA/D. Nonetheless, the method's performance coupled with orthogonal distances is relatively poor. The reason is that the orthogonal distance accounts only for distribution, not convergence. Unlike NSGA-III, which handles the convergence by employing non-dominated sorting, MOEA/D relies on the optimization goals when handling both the distribution and convergence. Therefore, such scalarized functions as PBI or the Chebyshev function are more suited for MOEA/D.

Figure 34: Results attained by MOEA/D applied to DTLZ2 (orthogonal distances)

Figure 35: Results attained by MOEA/D applied to DTLZ2 (Chebyshev functions)

Figure 36: Results attained by MOEA/D applied to DTLZ2 (penalty-based boundary intersection functions with the aggregating coefficient of 5.0)

Figure 37: Results attained by MOEA/D applied to WFG1 (orthogonal distances)

Figure 38: Results attained by MOEA/D applied to WFG1 (Chebyshev functions)

Figure 39: Results attained by MOEA/D applied to WFG1 (penalty-based boundary intersection functions with the aggregating coefficient of 5.0)

3.5. Comparative analysis [T]

Source package:
t1_t10.t3_evolutionary_multiobjective_optimization.t5_comparative

This tutorial showcases how to employ all the introduced algorithms – NSGA, NSGA-II, NSGA-III, and MOEA/D – in a comparative analysis. Let me highlight again that this tutorial intends to illustrate how to employ the methods rather than to show how to perform a methodologically correct and complete experimental analysis (this will be discussed in later tutorial documents).

The experimental setup follows the settings used in the preceding sections, with the following changes:

- This time, all the methods are employed simultaneously and compared.
- Apart from the HV indicator, the IGD and GD are also used (the reference points were generated using the filtering-based random sampling approach – the orthogonal distances to reference lines were used to find the best performers). The scatter plots are not illustrated. The source codes generate just convergence plots that exhibit the methods' performance over generations.
- The number of objectives involved equals 2, . . . 5.
- The limit for the number of generations is dependent on the number of objectives.
- The population sizes are unified, i.e., are the same for all methods within one experimental scenario. Since the population size for the decomposition-based methods results from the number of points generated by Das and Dennis' method, the population size for NSGA and NSGA-II was adjusted to match their decomposition-based competitors.

The expected final outcomes of the tutorial's source codes are presented in Figures 40 (DTLZ2) and 41 (WFG1). Several observations that are consistent with the well-known facts about the examined methods can be made (note that their credibility is relatively poor as they were obtained by executing the algorithms just once):

- The decomposition-based methods often prove superior to the dominance-based ones – especially in many dimensional scenarios.
- The search imposed by the decomposition-based methods is more stable and consistent.
- The performance of NSGA-II deteriorates with the increase in the number of objectives when tackling the DTLZ2 problem – making it worse than NSGA. In turn, the NSGA-II performs better than NSGA when dealing with WFG1.

- MOEA/D performs better than NSGA-III in the simpler DTLZ2 problem. Vice versa, NSGA-III seems superior in the WFG1 scenario. The reason is that the fitness landscape of WFG1 imposes less uniform search, which may promote methods with less rigorous control over the evolutionary process imposed (MOEA/D is focused more on exploitation than exploration due to (1) the steady-state mode and (2) using a restricted mating pool).

References

- [1] K. Deb, A. Pratap, S. Agarwal, and T. Meyarivan, "A fast and elitist multiobjective genetic algorithm: NSGA-II," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 182–197, 2000.
- [2] K. Deb, L. Thiele, M. Laumanns, and E. Zitzler, *Scalable Test Problems for Evolutionary Multiobjective Optimization*, pp. 105–145. London: Springer London, 2005.
- [3] S. Huband, P. Hingston, L. Barone, and L. While, "A review of multiobjective test problems and a scalable test problem toolkit," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 477–506, 2006.
- [4] Q. Zhang and H. Li, "MOEA/D: A multiobjective evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 712–731, 2007.
- [5] K. Deb and H. Jain, "An evolutionary many-objective optimization algorithm using reference-point-based nondominated sorting approach, part I: Solving problems with box constraints," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 577–601, 2014.
- [6] M. K. Tomczyk and M. Kadziński, "Decomposition-based coevolutionary algorithm for interactive multiple objective optimization," *Information Sciences*, vol. 549, pp. 178–199, 2021.
- [7] I. D. Das and J. E. Dennis, "Normal-boundary intersection: A new method for generating the Pareto surface in nonlinear multicriteria optimization problems," *SIAM Journal on Optimization*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 631–657, 1998.
- [8] L. While, L. Bradstreet, and L. Barone, "A fast way of calculating exact hypervolumes," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 86–95, 2012.
- [9] N. Srinivas and K. Deb, "Multiobjective optimization using nondominated sorting in genetic algorithms," *Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 221–248, 1994.
- [10] H. Seada, M. Abouhawwash, and K. Deb, "Multiphase balance of diversity and convergence in multiobjective optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 503–513, 2019.

Figure 40: Results of the comparative analysis (DTLZ2)

Figure 41: Results of the comparative analysis (WFG1)